

D7.1

Guidelines and specifications for soil biodiversity and soil health data capture

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Deliverable 7.1 Guidelines and specifications for soil biodiversity and soil health data capture

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Executive Summary

The European Union has clear guidelines regarding the importance of open data and the reuse of information from the public sector (DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/1024 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of June 20, 2019). On the other hand, the 2020 Program also establishes guidelines on the application of the FAIR principles for data management. Aligned with this general framework, the Soil O-live EU project has to deploy the particular actions necessary for its data production is consistent with this framework. Data are the objective basis of any investigation and of the current information and knowledge society.

This guide gathers information and provides guidance for a **harmonized field data collection** among all partners, as well as the **creation of metadata** (on ecology, biology and related areas), and the **elaboration of geospatial open data** in the framework of the project. Several **annexes** are included for providing further technical details supporting the information included in sections A, B and C of this report.

A. Instructions for collecting field data

In order to ensure adequate homogeneity and consistency of the field data of the project and to be able to integrate them into other European projects (LUCAS-Land Use and Coverage Area frame Survey), as well as the incorporation of metadata, it is necessary to complete the forms for each plot and sampling point.

The presented data corresponds to the result of the survey conducted on all researchers who will be collecting data in the field. These elements are common to all research areas.

The data from the form related to the working plot will only be taken once. To facilitate the understanding of the items, the following explanatory document is attached for each section.

A.1. Description of the items relating to the study plot

Plot identifier

Corresponds to the identifier assigned by the project manager for each plot.

SPAIN	GREECE	ITALY	MARROC	PORTUGAL
ES-HD2	GR-HD43	IT-ORG17	MR-HD25	PT-HD51
ES-HD3	GR-ORG32	IT-ORG18	MR-HD28	PT-HD52
ES-HD8	GR-ORG33	IT-ORG19_1	MR-ORG23	PT-HD53
ES-HD10	GR-ORG34	IT-ORG19_2	MR-TD24	PT-ORG42
ES-HD22	GR-ORG38	IT-ORG48	MR-TD26	PT-TD41
ES-HD40	GR-ORG39	IT-ORG49	MR-TD27	
ES-ORG4	GR-ORG45	IT-TD16	MR-TD29	
ES-ORG6	GR-ORG47	IT-TD20		
EN-ORG11	GR-TD30	IT-TD21		
EN-ORG12	GR-TD31	IT-TD50		
EN-ORG13	GR-TD35			
EN-ORG14	GR-TD36			
ES-TD1	GR-TD37			
ES-TD5	GR-TD44			
ES-TD7	GR-TD46			
ES-TD9				
ES-TD15				

Estimated age of the olive grove

0.1. Very young olive grove (0-10 years)
0.2. Young olive grove (10-20)
0.3. Mature olive grove (20-50)
0.4. Old olive grove (50-100)
0.5. Very old olive grove (more than 100)

Plantation frame

Relative to the planting distance between olive trees following a pattern. Options:

A: In hedge:

Row distance: (a)

Distance between trunks (b)

B: Rectangular frame. Measure the distance between two trees.

C: Irregular planting. Does not follow any pattern.

Olive tree variety

ADRAMITINI	1	LADOLIA	11
ARBEQUINA	2	NOCELLARA DEL BELICE	12
ARDUO	3	PICHOLINE LANGUEDOC	13
CERASUOLA	4	PICHOLINE MAROCAINE	14
COBRANÇOSA	5	PICUAL	15
GIARRAFFA	6	PICUDO	16
HAOUZIA MENARA	7	SIKITITA	17
HOJIBLANCA	8	THROUBOLIA	18
KOLOVI	9	other	19
KORONÉIKI	10		

Number of trunks of the olive tree

One, two or three trunks.

Average production data

If the data is known, indicate it (Kg/ha).

Irrigation

If the plot has an irrigation system, indicate it (Yes/No)

Photograph of the plot

When possible, according to LUCAS directive.

A.2. Description of the items relating to the sampling points

WP code

It corresponds to the Soil O-live project work package or task code. i.e. WP5 , T5.3, T4.1.

Date and time

Incorporate the date and time following the ISO 8601 standard: year-month-day (YYYY-MM-DD), hh:mm:ss (Hour (H) hh , from 00 to 23, 24:00:00 as last minute).

GPS coordinates of the sample point

General indications:

1. Identify the WayPoints: Put an identifier to each sample point in the GPS
2. Do not take points under trees with a large crown diameter, since the GPS signal decreases. If necessary, take several points around the tree.
3. Wait a few seconds until the accuracy improves (greater number of satellites available)
4. To obtain a more accurate altitude (Z) place the GPS on the ground when taking the point
5. Data download: as far as possible, download the GPS track points to the computer (if you don't know how to do it, contact the WP 7.1 team, tell us the GPS model and we will tell you how to do it)
6. Put the following configuration in the GPS:

-To unify the coordinates of all the sampling points, the WGS84 World Geodetic System (World geodetic System 1984) decimal degrees (DD) (with six decimal digits)

-Do NOT use UTM projected coordinates, as it can cause confusion when using different ZONES depending on the country in which you work.

Settings:

Satellite system	GPS+GLONASS WAAS/ egnos : on
Time	Choose 24 hour time setting. Time Zone: automatic
Units	Metric Elevation meters
Position format (Latitude / longitude) ¹	Hddd.ddddd = decimal degrees (6 decimal places)
Datum	WGS84
Map spheroid	WGS84
Heading	Numeric degrees North reference: true

Vegetable cover

It refers to the existence of herbaceous vegetation (size greater than 10 cm) in the plot at the time of sampling: (yes/no)

¹h = Hemisphere (**North** , **South** , **East** , or **West**)
d = Degree

Phenological status of the olive grove

Indicate the identifying letter of the phenological state of the olive tree:

A.- Sprouting or spring bud.	B.- Development of leaf buds	C.- Flowering.
D.- Formation of the fruit.	E.- Development of the fruit.	F.- Veraison.
G. -Ripening.	H.- Picked fruit	I.- Pruning

Weather data of the day of field data capture

Although the data is imprecise, this information can be very useful to validate data collection. Mobile phones can provide us with information related to temperature. Precipitation and wind should be a subjective perception as there are no meters of these variables, however, the Beaufort classification in the case of wind will be taken as a reference, and the following Standard AEMET table for precipitation:

Temperature	Precipitation					Wind (Beaufort Scale)
	D.	m	F	MF	you	

Beaufort number	description	Wind speed	country conditions
0	calm	<2km/h	Smoke rises vertically
1	Light air	2–5 km/h	Direction shown by smoke drift but not by wind vanes
2	Light breeze	6–11 km/h	Wind felt on face; leaves rustle; wind vane moved by wind
3	Gentle breeze	12–19 km/h	Leaves and small twigs in constant motion; light flags extended
4	Moderate breeze	20–28 km/h	Raises dust and loose paper; small branches moved
5	Fresh breeze	29–38 km/h	Small trees in leaf begin to sway; crested wavelets form on inland waters
6	strong breeze	39–49 km/h	Large branches in motion; whistling heard in telegraph wires; umbrellas used with difficulty
7	High wind, moderate gale, near gale	50–61 km/h	Whole trees in motion; inconvenience felt when walking against the wind
8	Gale, fresh Gale	62–74 km/h	Twigs break off trees; generally impedes progress
9	Strong's /severe gale	75–88 km/h	Slight structural damage (chimney pots and slates removed)
10	Storm , whole gale	89–102 km/h	Seldom experienced inland; trees uprooted; considerable structural damage
eleven	violent storm	103–117 km/h	Very rarely experienced; accompanied by widespread damage
12	Hurricane - force [13]	≥118km/h	Devastation

Precipitation according to its intensity

Class	Average intensity in one hour (mm/h)
Weak	≤2
Moderate	>2 and ≤15
Powerful	>15 and ≤30
Very strong	>30 and ≤60
Torrential	>60

Sampling type

d	linear	e	linear	s1	Random on regular surface
s2	Stratified on regular surface	s3	On a grid	s4	zig Zag
s5	crossed	s6	traced	s7	grid center
s8	Regular points on circular surface	p1	Random points on plot	p2	Intersection point
p3	Square center point	p4	under tree		other

Distance to the tree from the sample point

Measure the distance from the trunk to the sampling point in cm.

Sample depth

Measure the depth of the sample point and specify units (cm, mm, etc.).

Data of the people who take the field data

It is very important to identify the person who performs the data collection in the field, for this, it is necessary to attach the contact information of this person: name, telephone, mail.

Observations

Reserved field to record incidents related to georeferenced data that are not specific to the research area (weather incidents, GPS, etc.).

Data collection sheet (template)

Next, we provide a possible template to data collection with farms managers.

STUDY PLOT			
1.- PLOT IDENTIFIER			
2.- ESTIMATED AGE OF THE OLIVE GROVE	Very young olive grove (0-10 years)		
	Young olive grove (10-20 years)		
	Mature olive grove (20-50 years)		
	Old olive grove (50-100 years)		
	Very old olive grove (more than 100 years)		
3.- PLANTATION FRAMEWORK	In hedge:	Row width: (a)	
		Distance between trunks (b)	
	Rectangle frame	Distance between two trees	
	Irregular planting		
4.- VARIETY OF THE OLIVE TREE			
5.- NUMBER OF TRUNKS WITHIN THE OLIVE TREE (check all that apply)	One trunk	Two trunks	Three trunks
6.- AVERAGE PRODUCTION DATA			
7.- IRRIGATION:	Yes	No	
8.- OBSERVATIONS			

SAMPLING POINTS			
1.-WP Code:			
2.-Date			
3.-Time			
4.-GPS coordinates	Latitude	Longitude	
5.-Vegetal cover	Yes		No
6.-Phenological state of the olive grove (1 to 9)			
7.-Climatic data	Temperature	Precipitation	Wind
8.- Sampling type			
9.-Distance to the tree from the sample point (cm)			
10.- Sample depth			
11.- Person who takes data in the field	Name:		
	Surname:		
	Phone:		
	Email:		
12.-Observations			

Description of the study plots

In Annex 1, Soil O-live plots are characterized by using these descriptors.

B. Metadata creation

B.1. Introduction

The European Union has clear guidelines regarding the importance of open data and the reuse of information from the public sector (DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/1024 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 20 June 2019). Additionally, the 2020 Program also establishes guidelines for the implementation of FAIR principles (see [Annex 2](#)) in data management. Aligned with this general framework, the European project: "The soil biodiversity and functionality of Mediterranean olive groves: a holistic analysis of the influence of land management on olive oil quality and safety" (SOIL O-LIVE) must Develop and implement specific actions to ensure that its data production is consistent with this framework.

The objective of this guide is to provide guidance for metadata development within the framework of the SOIL O-live Project. Data serves as the objective basis for any research, and metadata plays a fundamental role in the efficient management of data by providing essential information about its origin, quality, content, structure, etc.

In the context of the SOIL O-live project, it is crucial to have accurate and consistent metadata that enables interoperability and information exchange among the various stakeholders involved. Additionally, these metadata should facilitate the future reuse of the data by other researchers. This guide provides the necessary guidelines for SOIL O-live project participants to properly document and describe the datasets related to the studies conducted within the project, following recognized European standards and best practices.

Throughout the guide, various aspects related to metadata creation will be addressed, including practical examples and recommendations to facilitate their development.

Importance of incorporating metadata in ecology and other sciences

Researchers in life sciences (zoologists, ecologists, botanists, etc.) are increasingly using data collected by other scientists to address questions at broader spatial, temporal, and thematic scales (e.g., global change, biodiversity, sustainability). In order to do so, research data from third parties must be accessible, allowing for result validation and experiment reproducibility.

If created data is not properly stored and reported, it can be lost. Merely saving tables and results is insufficient because no dataset explains itself, and researchers must therefore include instructions or documentation that enables data interpretation.

With a classical perspective on scientific production linked to the researcher, Figure 1 illustrates the concept of data degradation in a research project over time. This situation is undesirable and cannot be allowed, especially when the data has been generated with public funding.

Figure: Degradation of information associated with data and metadata over time ("information entropy") [Michener et al., 1997]:

In order for data to be useful in the future, it is important to accompany them with metadata.

"Metadata" is information. (Metadata is the documentation that describes the content, context, quality, structure, and accessibility of a dataset.)

The main benefits of incorporating metadata in a scientific research project are:

- They help locate and understand the data to decide the best way to use them.
- They allow for sharing information with others (researchers, institutions, etc.).
- The value of the data will be directly related to the documentation they include.
- Preserving the context in which they were created.

In general, metadata is the information that describes the "who, what, when, where, why, and how" of a dataset. Typically, metadata for observational data focuses on:

- What is the content of the data?
- Who collected the data?
- When were the data collected?
- Where were the data collected?
- How were the data collected?

It is crucial to collect and record metadata at the beginning of the research life cycle and have them complete in each phase of the research to prevent the loss of information that may be necessary in the future.

Assuming that almost all captured ecological data is valuable and should be preserved for the future, the challenge remains to determine which metadata are essential.

Fortunately, the process that scientists usually follow to acquire and use datasets often serves as a guide for determining the necessary metadata. Section 8 presents a minimum content.

The obligation of incorporating metadata in EU-funded projects. Considered standards and documents

The following documents, either in their entirety or in part, are essential for the implementation of this document.

1. Agreement signed between the EUROPEAN RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY (REA) and the participants of the SOIL O-live project

GRANT AGREEMENT. Project 101091255 - SOIL O-live. EUROPEAN RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY (REA) (p. 11, Open Science)

This document establishes the following points regarding the management of data generated within the project:

- Open access to publications in a reliable repository for scientific publications.
- Information on any research output or any other tools and instruments necessary to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication will be provided through the repository.
- Metadata for deposited publications must be openly available under Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in accordance with the FAIR principles (see [Annex 2](#)) (particularly machine-actionable), and provide information on at least the following: publication (author(s), title, publication date, place of publication); funding from Horizon Europe or Euratom; grant project name, acronym, and number; license terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organizations and the grant. When applicable, metadata should include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments necessary to validate the conclusions of the publication.

2. The SOIL O-live Project falls within the Horizon Europe Program of the European Commission

Horizon Europe (HORIZON) is the European Union's Framework Program for research and innovation, designed to promote scientific excellence, technological advancements, and innovation across various fields.

Proper management of research data is mandatory for any Horizon Europe project that generates or reuses research data. It is a key part of the open science requirements of Horizon Europe.

In Horizon Europe, beneficiaries must responsibly manage the digital research data generated in the action ("data") in accordance with the FAIR principles, and they must at least:

- Prepare a Data Management Plan (DMP) and keep it up to date throughout the project.
- Deposit data in a trusted repository and provide open access to them ("as open as possible, as closed as necessary").
- Provide information (through the same repository) on any research output or any other tools and instruments necessary for data reuse or validation.

Additionally, they must:

Provide open access to research data. This requirement, called the Open Research Data Pilot, applies to:

- Other selected and/or raw data (and metadata) specified in the DMP.

Participants of the Open Research Data Pilot must comply with:

1. Deposit the research data necessary to validate the results presented in scientific publications, including associated metadata, in the repository as soon as possible. Other data (e.g., data that cannot be directly attributed to a publication or raw data), including associated metadata, must also be deposited according to the individual judgment of each project, as specified in the data management plan.
2. Take measures to enable third parties to access, extract, exploit, reproduce, and disseminate (free of charge to any user) these research data, e.g., by attaching a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license to the deposited data or waiving all interests associated with copyright and database protection using the CCO tool. The EUDAT B2SHARE tool includes a built-in license assistant that facilitates the selection of an appropriate license for research data.
3. Provide information through the chosen repository about available tools for beneficiaries to validate results, e.g., specialized software or software code, algorithms, and analysis protocols. Whenever possible, these tools or instruments should be provided. (<https://www.openaire.eu/guides>)

B.2. Object and scope

The objective of this guide is to provide applied guidelines for metadata development within the SOIL O-live project, specifically for the fields of ecology, biology, and other related areas, concerning all data that does not have access restrictions.

B.3. Regulation

- Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast)
- Directive 2007/2/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 March 2007 establishing an Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community (INSPIRE)
- Commission Decision on the reuse of Commission documents (2011/833/EU)

- Commission Communication on better access to scientific information (COM/2012/0401 final)
- Commission Recommendation on access to and preservation of scientific information (2012/417/EU)

B.4. Terms and definitions

DOI Digital Object Identifier. A code used to permanently and stably identify (usually digital) objects. DOIs provide a standard mechanism for retrieval of metadata about the object, and generally a means to access the data object itself.

FAIR Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable.

INTEROPERABILITY The ability of data or tools from non-cooperating resources to integrate or work together with minimal effort.

METADATA Metadata refers to descriptive information that provides context and details about data. It includes attributes such as title, author, date, format, and other relevant characteristics that help organize, manage, and understand the data.

B.5. Basic metadata to be included in the Soil O-live project

Taking into account the guidelines of the Horizon Europe Program of the European Commission, as well as the FAIR principles, the minimum basic information that should be included in the general metadata of the Soil O-live project are as follows:

Data identification: Information regarding the content of the project data that allows for proper identification.

Resource title: Name by which the cited resource is known.
Resource abstract: Brief narrative summary of the content of the resource(s) with coverage, main attributes, data sources, importance of the work, etc.
Resource type: Scope to which metadata applies.
Resource Locator: URL address to locate the data.
Keyword: Tags commonly used for ad-hoc organization of content.

Geographical location: Information regarding the place where the data was collected.

Bounding Box: Coordinates of the four (West, East, North, South) foremost corners of the dataset.
Coverage: Coordinates of the four (West, East, North, South) foremost corners of the dataset.
Geotags: The exact geographic names/places that are covered by the data.
Coordinate Reference System: CRS (Coordinate Reference System) of the resource

Temporal reference: Information regarding the data collection time and project duration.

Temporal extent: The time period covered by the content of the resource. Project starting date and project end date. Date of publication.

Data quality, reliability, and reproducibility:

Lineage: In the context of the project, lineage refers to the trajectory of the data from its origin to its current state. It is a record of the processes and manipulations that have been applied to the data, including the data sources used, the modifications made, and the people or tools involved in each study area and project stage.

Lineage can be documented through records, metadata, process descriptions, flowcharts, or other tools that allow for clear and precise visualization and communication of the data history and applied transformations.

Access and usage limitations:

Conditions applying to access and use: Restrictions on the access and use of a resource or metadata.
Limitation of public access: Limitations and other reasons for public access.

Responsible organizations:

Responsible party: Organization associated with the resource. Organization name, contact information (email).

Temporal reference:

Temporal extent: The time period covered by the content of the resource.
Date of publication.

Taking into account this content framework, an example of the general metadata for the Soil O-live project has been developed in [Annex 3](#).

B.6. Specific metadata for different research areas of the Soil O-live project

For each of the research areas included in the SOIL O-Live project, it is necessary to create metadata tailored to the specific theme, comprehensive, and accessible.

These metadata are essential for the dissemination, preservation, and impact generation of the results, which is why a high level of involvement is required from the participating researchers.

Researchers are recommended to consider the following guidelines for efficient data management:

- Store the "raw" data in formats that allow for storage, transmission, and sharing of open data.
- Always document the original data and statistics with written reports.
- Document the processes and their results to which the data are subjected.

The participating researchers in the SOIL O-Live project and the data archive administrators have the responsibility to ensure that the metadata are available freely and comprehensively.

Basic metadata to be included in the ecology and other sciences area

The table below presents the minimum set of metadata recommended by CIEEM (Chartered Institute of Ecology and Environmental Management) for environmental studies.

Table. Set of metadata recommended by (Chartered Institute of Ecology and Environmental Management (CIEEM). Data source: CIEEM, 2020

Topic	Detail of metadata to accompany data/survey report	Included Yes/No
Title	Title of the dataset (typically including taxa, data type, date(s) and geographical extent of information)	
Subject	A shortlist of key words that describe the dataset	
Language	Language used in the dataset if not English (Spanish, French, Portuguese)	
Abstract	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · A clear and concise statement that enables the reader to understand the content of the dataset · Circumstances leading to data collection · Explicit aims of the survey(s) yielding the data · Brief overview of dataset content 	
Ownership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ownership and copyright of data - Contact name and address for further information and support to facilitate access to, and use of, data 	
Survey date	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Date(s) of data collection (DD/MM/YY) as single date(s) or range - Time of day of start / finish and weather conditions (if relevant and not part of methods e.g., birds transect) - Frequency of update if survey is ongoing 	
Location	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Name of the site(s), and country - Longitudinal and latitudinal bounds of survey extent if sample points are widely scattered - Site description (major habitats and altitudinal range if this information is not part of data set) - Site ownership and access (where possible) 	

Topic	Detail of metadata to accompany data/survey report	Included Yes/No
Survey personnel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Name(s) of field surveyors and organization(s) - Experience of surveyors in the methods used - Qualifications, professional memberships and licenses held 	
Field methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Description of methods sufficient to permit repetition and assess adequacy of sampling design - Detailed site map showing location of sample points, transects and/or routes followed during walk surveys - Reference to published manuals and project specific modifications to standard methods - Brief justification of the approach taken 	
Data descriptors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data presentation type (e.g., digital map or spreadsheet) - Definition of the data variables - Units of measurement - Precision of measurements (e.g., to one decimal point) - Spatial resolution (e.g., minimum mappable unit) and for GIS records spatial representation (e.g., vector or grid) - Spatial reference system used in data (e.g., WGS84) - Detailed key to data labels where abbreviations are used in dataset (e.g., in rows and columns of spreadsheet) - Full reference to species identification keys and habitat classifications used - Taxonomic authority cited for scientific binomials 	
Data processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Name(s) of dataset compiler(s) and organization(s) - Date of dataset compilation (DD/MM/YY) - Description of any processing of data after collection (e.g., error correction) and name/version of any software utilized (e.g., GIS package) - Justification for processing decisions 	

Topic	Detail of metadata to accompany data/survey report	Included Yes/No
Quality assurance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Methods used to determine accuracy of observations, and species identification during survey (e.g., re-sampling) - Post-survey assessments of data reliability (e.g., adequacy of sample size) - Conclusions drawn from these QA procedures; including, for example, quantitative estimates of data accuracy. 	
Data archiving and usage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Location of the “raw” data - Name, date and version of computer software with which data have been saved and file type (e.g. .doc,.bmp) - Restrictions on access to the data - Constraints on use of the data - Record of changes to data and metadata with name and organization of editor(s) - Details of reports/publications describing or using the data - Additional sources of information (e.g., publications or websites that describe background to the project or data) 	

Example of metadata in areas of ecology, chemistry, etc.

There are numerous examples of studies in the field of sciences that include metadata.

Example:

Soil carbon storage, soil quality and biodiversity data of nine permaculture plots and direct control fields in Central Europe (2019-2021).

<https://search.dataone.org/view/doi%3A10.5063%2FF1J964VN>

DATASET | PUBLISHED 2023 | DOI:10.5063/F1J964VN

Soil carbon storage, soil quality and biodiversity data of nine permaculture plots and direct control fields in Central Europe (2019–2021)

Julius Reiff, Hermann Jungkunst, Ken M. Mauser, Sophie Kampel, Sophie Regending, Verena Rösch, Johann G. Zaller, and Martin H. Entling

Downloads Citations Views Cite this dataset Assessment report

Name	File type	Size	Download
Metadata: Soil_carbon_storage_soil_quality_and.xml	EML v2.2.0	38 KB	Download
data_soil.csv	text/csv	19 KB	Download
data_bio.csv	text/csv	703 B	Download
data_birds.csv	text/csv	197 B	Download

Title /data set

General

Annotations: Data Sensitivity Category: **Non-sensitive data**

Identifier: doi:10.5063/F1J964VN

Abstract: In this study, we examined eight permaculture plots in Germany and one in Luxembourg one time each from 2019 to 2021. These plots represented either entire farms or sections of farms. The permaculture plots were designed and managed according to permaculture principles, with the goal of achieving economic self-sufficiency in production. They also integrated at least two different types of land use, such as grazing and fruit trees. The specific number and types of land use varied among the permaculture plots.

For each location, we collected soil samples from one field representing each permaculture land use type, as well as one control field that reflected the locally predominant agricultural land use. We analyzed the soil samples to assess soil carbon and various nutrients. Additionally, we examined the microbial community structure using phospholipid fatty acids and assessed earthworm abundance. We also measured soil bulk density and depth of humic topsoil.

In terms of biodiversity, we investigated the species richness of vascular plants, earthworms and birds. We also determined if areas were covered by trees or not.

Publication Date: 2023

Identifier/Abstract

People and Associated Parties

Data Set Creators

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People and Associated parties: data set creators

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	Id	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6152-994X

Data set contacts

Geographic Region	
Geographic Description	Germany, Luxembourg
Bounding Coordinates	North 53.76893686673942 degrees
	South 47.68842327777589 degrees
	East 15.416363454268623 degrees
	West 5.726422048086771 degrees

Geographic region

Temporal Coverage	
Date Range	Begin 2019
	End 2021

Temporal coverage

Methods & Sampling	
Methods	Step 1
Description	No method step description provided. We will include a citation of the relevant journal article.
Sampling	Sampling Step 1
Sampling Area And Frequency	In this research, we examined a total of nine permaculture plots in Germany and Luxembourg between 2019 and 2021. These plots were either standalone farms or sections of larger farms. The permaculture plots were required to adhere to permaculture principles in their design and management, achieve economic self-sufficiency in production, and incorporate at least two different types of land use, such as grazing and fruit trees. The number and types of land use varied across the permaculture plots. For each location, we selected one field representing each type of permaculture land use, as well as one control field with the prevailing local agricultural land use.
Sampling Description	No sampling description provided.

Methods & sampling

Data set

Entity Name **data_soil.csv**

[Download](#)

Data Object Type: text/csv Attribute(s) Info:

Name	location
Annotations	contains measurements of type study location identifier
Label	Contains Measurements Of Type Study Location Identifier
Definition	Attribute location in otherEntity data_soil.csv contains measurements of type study location identifier
Storage Type	Find more information about this term at http://ecoinformatics.org/obo/owl#containsMeasurementsOfType
Measurement Type	Find more information about this term at http://purl.dataone.org/odo/ECSO_00002767 .
Measurement Domain	Find more datasets with annotations of study location identifier .
Missing Value Code	
Accuracy Report	
Accuracy Assessment	
Coverage	
Methods & Sampling	

Variables

- location
- farm
- landuse
- plot
- age
- ah_depth
- texture_10
- texture_30
- ph_10
- ph_30
- bulk_10
- bulk_30
- corg_10
- corg_30
- n_10
- n_30
- p2o5_10

The screenshot shows a metadata editor for the variable 'texture_10'. The left sidebar lists various variables, with 'texture_10' selected. The main panel displays the following details:

- Annotations:** contains measurements of type **soil texture**
- Label:** (empty)
- Definition:** Soil texture of the 0-10 cm soil layer according to the Association of Agricultural Chemists (AAC) method, which is divided into seven soil texture classes with decreasing particle size from top to bottom. Source: Soil Science Society of America, Soil Science Society of Europe, and Soil Science Society of Japan.
- Storage Type:** (empty)
- Measurement Type:** ordinal
- Measurement Domain:** Enumerated Domain

A tooltip for 'Soil Texture' is visible, providing additional information and a link to find more datasets with annotations of soil texture.

Code	Definition	Source
1	S	
2	sLS	
3	LS	
4	sL	
5	LU	
6	tL	
7	T	

The screenshot shows a metadata editor for the variable 'n_10'. The left sidebar lists various variables, with 'n_10' selected. The main panel displays the following details:

- Annotations:** contains measurements of type **nitrogen concentration in soil**
- Label:** (empty)
- Definition:** Nitrogen concentration in soil (N₁₀) is the amount of nitrogen (N) in the soil per 100 gram soil dry matter. Source: International Geosphere and Biosphere Programme (IGBP) Global Change and Terrestrial Ecosystems (GCTE) Program on Soil Science (PSS).
- Storage Type:** (empty)
- Measurement Type:** (empty)
- Measurement Domain:** (empty)

Two tooltips are visible, providing additional information and links to find more datasets with annotations of nitrogen concentration in soil.

Can find more examples at the following URLs

- <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/chemical-properties-european-scale-based-lucas-topsoil-data>
- <https://catalogue.ceh.ac.uk/documents/b330d395-68f2-47f1-8d59-3291dc02923b>
- <https://search.dataone.org/view/doi%3A10.5063%2FF1J964VN>
- <https://ecm.ac.uk/data/available-data>

Basic metadata to include in geographic data area

In the field of geospatial data, there is extensive experience in metadata creation and a well-established framework in the European Union through the Inspire Directive and its specific implementation rules for metadata (<https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/Technical-Guidelines2/Metadata/6541>). The creation of this type of metadata will be governed entirely by this regulation.

B.7. Tools for creating metadata files

There are various tools available for creating metadata for ecological data. In this project, we have selected the open-source software "Morpho," but if someone is familiar with another tool, there is no problem in using it as long as it can be incorporate the previously described items.

Morpho is an application designed for creating metadata in ecology, but it is also suitable for other areas such as chemistry, soil science, etc. The information is stored in the Ecological Metadata Language (EML), and it allows the export of metadata to HTML.

To download this application, please visit: <http://knb.ecoinformatics.org/morphoportal.jsp>

You do not need to register on the KNB network (data repository) because the data repository to be used is ZENODO EU. Therefore, you should store your metadata files locally on your computer and then send them to sig_soilolive@ujaen.es so that we can register them in Zenodo.

Annex 4 includes the basic steps for creating metadata with Morpho.

(The Morpho user guide can be accessed at

<https://knb.ecoinformatics.org/software/dist/MorphoUserGuide.pdf>)

In the field of geospatial data, there are numerous FOSS tools available for generating metadata, such as GeoNode, CatMDEdit, GeoNetwork, etc. Any of these options is valid for this project.

C. Open publication of geospatial data

C.1. Introduction

The European Union has clear guidelines regarding the importance of open data and the reuse of information from the public sector (DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/1024 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of June 20, 2019). On the other hand, the 2020 Program also establishes guidelines on the application of the FAIR principles (see annex I) for data management. Aligned with this general framework, the European project: The soil biodiversity and functionality of Mediterranean olive groves: a holistic analysis of the influence of land management on olive oil quality and safety (SOIL O-LIVE) must deploy the particular actions necessary for its data production is consistent with this framework.

The objective of this guide is to provide guidance for the elaboration of geospatial open data in the framework of the SOIL O-Live Project. Data are the objective basis of any investigation and of the current information and knowledge society. For the Opendata (<https://opengovdata.org/>) data shall be considered open if it is made public in a way that complies with the principles below:

- **Complete.** All public data is made available. Public data is data that is not subject to valid privacy, security or privilege limitations.
- **Primary.** Data is as collected at the source, with the highest possible level of granularity, not in aggregate or modified forms.
- **Timely.** Data is made available as quickly as necessary to preserve the value of the data.
- **Accessible.** Data is available to the widest range of users for the widest range of purposes.
- **Machine processable.** Data is reasonably structured to allow automated processing.
- **Non-discriminatory.** Data is available to anyone, with no requirement of registration.
- **Non-proprietary.** Data is available in a format over which no entity has exclusive control.
- **License-free.** Data is not subject to any copyright, patent, trademark or trade secret regulation. Reasonable privacy, security and privilege restrictions may be allowed.

Seven additional principles have been added:

- **Online & Free.** Information is not meaningfully public if it is not available on the Internet at no charge, or at least no more than the marginal cost of reproduction. It should also be findable.
- **Permanent.** Data should be made available at a stable Internet location indefinitely and in a stable data format for as long as possible.
- **Trusted.** The Association of Computing Machinery's Recommendation on Open Government (February 2009) stated, "Published content should be digitally signed or include attestation of publication/creation date, authenticity, and integrity." Digital signatures help the public validate the source of the data they find so that they can trust that the data has not been modified since it was published. Since provenance is for originally-published documents, it is not a reason to prevent the public from modifying government documents.

- A Presumption of Openness. The presumption of openness rests on laws like the Freedom of Information Act, procedures including records management, and tools such as data catalogs.
- Documented. Documentation about the format and meaning of data goes a long way to making the data useful.
- Safe to Open. The Association of Computing Machinery’s Recommendation on Open Government (February 2009) stated, “Government bodies publishing data online should always seek to publish using data formats that do not include executable content.”
- Designed with Public Input. The public is in the best position to determine what information technologies will be best suited for the applications the public intends to create for itself. Public input is therefore crucial to disseminating information in such a way that it has value.

In the context of the SOIL O-Live project, it is proposed to generate open geospatial data and metadata sets that allow interoperability and the exchange of information between the different actors involved and that, in addition, facilitate the future reuse of these data by others. researchers. This guide provides the participants of the SOIL O-Live project with the necessary guidelines to generate open geospatial data sets within the tasks that have this purpose, following the standards and best practices recognized at a European level.

Throughout the guide, various aspects related to the creation of open data will be addressed, in addition to including practical examples and recommendations to facilitate its preparation.

C.2. Object and scope

The objective of this guide is to provide applied guidelines so that, within the SOIL O-Live project, the publication of geospatial data sets can be considered “open”. This guide is valid for all the topics that the SOIL O-Live project develops (e.g. ecology, biology, etc.), and for all those data sets that do not have access restrictions.

C.3. Regulation

The following rules apply in this document:

- Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast).
- Directive 2007/2/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 March 2007 establishing an Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community (INSPIRE).

C.4. Terms and definitions

The following terms and definitions apply in this document:

DOI Digital Object Identifier. A code used to permanently and stably identify (usually digital) objects. DOIs provide a standard mechanism for retrieval of metadata about the object, and generally a means to access the data object itself.

FAIR Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable.

INTEROPERABILITY The ability of data or tools from non-cooperating resources to integrate or work together with minimal effort.

C.5. Abbreviated terms

The following abbreviated terms are used in this document:

CC Creative commons.

ISO International Organization for Standardization.

C.6. Open publication of geospatial data in the Soil O-live project

The publication of open geospatial data in the SOIL O-Live Project follows the general principles of FAIR. The publication of open geospatial data within the SOIL O-Live Project supposes the conjunction of the following:

1. Data set. Data sets created within the SOIL O-Live project that do not have access restrictions (e.g. personal data, confidential data, etc.) These data are created by those responsible for the project's activities following the standards of their areas of competence.
2. Metadata. Metadata is a fundamental part of open data since it provides the appropriate semantics and context to understand the characteristics of the data set (origin, processes, quality, quantities, etc.) that are the basis for decision-making: to use or not that data set, use it under certain conditions, etc. For everything related to metadata, the "Deliverable /1 Part A "Guide for metadata" should be consulted, which forms an indissoluble pair with this document.
3. License. Application license to the data set and compatible with the FAIR guidelines.
4. Format. Physical data recording format that is not linked to brands or specific payment tools.
5. Repository. Place in which the data is deposited and that through searches allows access to the metadata, data and the download of the data and metadata.

Items 3, 4 and 5 are the scope of this guide, which are presented below.

Licenses for open geospatial data sets

The stipulations governing the SOIL O-Live project contract establish that the publication of the data sets must be carried out "under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or a license with equivalent rights, following the principle 'as open as possible as closed as necessary', unless providing open access would in particular".

Figure below presents a general outline of what each of the CC licenses allows. Framed with a red border, the licenses to be used are indicated. In this link <https://creativecommons.org/faq/> you can find valuable information to clarify your doubts about the different licenses.

Figure. Creative commons licenses overview (Source: <https://www.wur.nl/en/article/what-are-creative-commons-licenses.htm>)

File formats for open geospatial data sets

A key element for a geospatial data sets to be considered open, is the digital format that supports it. In this aspect, the basic idea is the use of formats that are not proprietary, that are well defined by some norm or standard and that are widely used. Below, for different types of data (vector, raster, LiDAR, etc.), the Table X indicates some recommended file formats. Currently, all these formats are supported by the GDAL (<https://gdal.org/>) library, which is widely used among open-source tools, both GIS (e.g. QGIS) and statistical (e.g. R). For the formats that GDAL works with, take a look at: <https://gdal.org/drivers/raster/index.htm>.

Type (Format)	Remarks
Vector	
ESRI Shapefile	Developed in the early 1990's, the shapefile format is used to store vector data in either points, lines, or polygons. The main shapefile with extension .shp must be accompanied by at least two other files with extensions .shx and .dbf. Often more than 3 files encompass a single shapefile, all with the same name but different extensions (denoting the different types of information stored in each). This file format requires field names shorter than 11 characters and file

	sizes less than 2 GB. When sharing these data, it is important to package all accompanying files in zip so they remain together.
GML	GML is an Extensible Markup Language (XML) structure for storing geographic features. Initially released in 2000, the GML format provided a way to standardize geospatial data being shared online. GML files can have the extension of either .gml, or .xml, and as with most XML structures, there is a separate schema file to describe the elements used in the data and the data itself. The GML schema offers metadata for coordinate reference systems, units of measure, and feature descriptors (for primitive objects like points, lines, polygons, and even curves). The schema is also extensible allowing for new feature descriptions of real-world objects like roads, bridges, etc. for use within a specific community. In 2007 GML became an ISO standard, with the official number ISO 19136:2007. GML is the default encoding for all INSPIRE (Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe, https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/about-inspire/563) spatial data themes. Though generally not considered for its ability to support raster data, GML files can also be used to georeference jpg2000 images (https://www.ogc.org/standards/gmljp2)
Keyhole Markup Language (KML)	KML is a derivative of GML used for styling of geographic information, and includes a specific set of features for use in Google Earth and Google Maps. Developed by Keyhole Inc. for use in their Keyhole Earth Viewer, Google acquired the company in 2004 and a year later released Google Earth. Features from the platform were also incorporated into Google Maps. These files are identified by the .kml extensions and a compressed version of KML has a .kmz extension. KML became an OGC standard in 2008 and as part of this standard, a camera view can be used to control what the user sees, add image overlays, captions and icons, differentiating it from other geospatial data standards.
GeoJSON	Leveraging JavaScript Object Notation (JSON), the GeoJSON file format has several defined geospatial datatypes used for easily sharing data online. Compared to XML, JSON files are smaller in size as they rely on key-value pairs instead of a tag-based structure. Recognized by the extension .json and .geojson, GeoJSON files can include vector data with one or more point, line, polygon, multi-point, and multi-line features. All GeoJSON files have the same geographic coordinate reference system (WGS84) simplifying the visualization of these data. Most web maps have libraries to view GeoJSON files, making it a great choice for sharing and visualizing data online.
Raster	
Geotiff	The combination of a Tag Image File Format (TIFF) with geospatial (i.e., location) information produces a GeoTIFF. The extension for these files is either .tif or .tiff, and upon first glance look like standard image files. The inclusion of geospatial information as part of TIFF files can be determined using a GIS or programmatically using GDAL.
Hierarchical Data Format (HDF)	HDF files are very versatile allowing researchers to store images, tables, graphs, and even documents within one file. Identified by files with the extension .hdf, .he5, and .h5, these files are comparable to a folder with a root level containing child folders and files within. These self-describing files can store multi-

		dimensional data and are useful for storing general-purpose scientific data. HDF5 is the latest version which is much more structured than the previous.
Network Common Data Format (NetCDF)	Format	Developed in 1980 for sharing atmospheric science data, the NetCDF file format has gained popularity across many scientific disciplines. NetCDF files have the file extension .netcdf, .nc, and .nc4. They can be used to store large numeric multi-dimensional datasets with a time-series and spatial component, making them great for computational model outputs. Like the Hierarchical Data Format (HDF), NetCDF files are self-describing ensuring that documentation accompanies the data when shared. A few organizations using NetCDF include NOAA, NASA and USGS.
DEM		
USGS, Canadian (.DEM)	DEM, CDED	The DEM format are raster-based ASCII files specifically developed by the USGS to capture digital elevation models. They are widely used in the industry because of the high volume of legacy elevation models produced by the USGS. The DEM format is a single file containing 3 record types. Record A stores general characteristics of the DEM such as descriptive name, elevation minimum and maximum, extent boundaries and number of B records. Record B contains a header and elevation profile. Record C stores the accuracy of the data and is optional.
Vector&Raster		
GeoPackage		Built upon the open-source database SQLite, GeoPackages provide a platform-independent, self-describing, and compact format that supports both raster tile matrix sets and vector data. These geospatial files have the extension .gpkg and can store many geospatial layers together in one compact file. Beyond sharing data with others, geopackages are useful for field data collection when internet access is intermittent or non-existent as data can be stored locally and later synced to a remote system.
LiDAR		
ASPRS LiDAR Data Exchange Format (.LAS, .LASD, .LAZ)		The LAS file format is a binary file format specifically for the interchange between vendors and customers. Overall, LAS files maintain information specific to LiDAR without the loss of information. LAS files are available for public use, unlike ASCII and other proprietary file formats. The dense networks of coordinate point measurements are so large sometimes that they often need to be split to prevent the file size from becoming too large. When you compress a LAS file, the file format specifically for this is LAZ. You can save significant storage space using the LAZ file format. Like most file compression, LAZ has no information loss. Lastly, LAS Datasets (LASD) reference a set of LAS files. The purpose of LASD is to be able to examine 3D point cloud properties from the referenced LAS files. Through LAS datasets, you can visualize triangulated surfaces and perform statistical analysis.
Point Cloud XYZ		XYZ files don't have specifications for storing point cloud data. The first 3 columns generally represent X, Y and Z coordinates. But there's no standard specification so it may include RGB, intensity values and other LiDAR values.

	They are in the ASCII point cloud group of file formats which includes TXT, ASC, and PTS. Non-binary files like XYZ are advantageous because they can be opened and edited in a text editor.
GNSS	
GPS eXchange Format (GPX)	GPS Exchange format is an XML schema that describes waypoints, tracks, and routes captured from a GPS receiver. Because GPX is an exchange format, you can openly transfer GPS data from one program to another based on its description properties. The minimum requirement for GPX are latitude and longitude coordinates. In addition, GPX files optionally stores location properties including time, elevation and geoid height as tags.
Data tables	
Comma Separated Values (CSV) and Tab Separated files (TSV)	<i>CSV or TSV files are plain text with columns of data separated by commas (or tabs) and each line represents a new record. Having a field or fields with census tracts, zip codes, or latitude and longitude values allows each record to be spatially aware. These files can be opened in any text editor, spreadsheet software or using programmatic methods. These files can be identified by the extension .csv or .tsv. It is best to include column names in the top line of these files, though it could be omitted (known as head-less files). Beyond a column header, documentation for these files generally remains separate. Efforts like the ICARTT standard (file extension .ict) have reserved a portion in the top of these files to more thoroughly describe each column of data, offering a self-describing option.</i>
SQL Database	
PostGIS + PostgreSQL	Open source PostGIS adds spatial objects to the cross-platform PostgreSQL database. The three features that PostGIS delivers to PostgreSQL DBMS are spatial types, indexes and functions. With support for different geometry types, the PostGIS spatial database allows querying and managing information about locations and mapping. PostGIS can be leveraged in several GIS software packages including QGIS, GRASS, ArcGIS, and MapInfo.
Georef Image	
Image	
Joint Photographic Experts Group JPEG2000 (.JP2)	JPEG 2000 typically have a JP2 file extension. They are a wavelet compression with the latest JPG format giving an option for lossy or lossless compression. JPEG 2000 GIS formats require a world file which gives your raster geolocation. They are an optimal choice for background imagery because of its lossy compression. JPEG 2000 can achieve a compression ratio of 20:1 which is similar to MrSID format.
Based on: https://libguides.colostate.edu/geospatial_file_formats and https://gisgeography.com/gis-formats/	

Repository for open data sets

Following the steps suggested by Openaire (Which repository to use? In <https://www.openaire.eu/find-trustworthy-data-repository>), in the SOIL O-Live project Zenodo will be used as a repository for all types of data sets generated in the Project. Zenodo is a “catch-all” repository maintained by CERN.

Zenodo is organized in communities. One has been opened for the soil o-live project. Within the communities you can upload resources of a wide variety of types (data sets, presentations, scientific articles, etc.). In a very summarized way, Zenodo offers storage in the cloud, a web application to search for resources and a metadata editor system for the resources that you want to share.

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INTRODUCTION

This document aims to provide a detailed description of the study plots that serve as the basis for the implementation of the Soil O-Live project, funded by the European Research Executive Agency (REA). This project focuses on the study of soil biodiversity and functionality in Mediterranean olive groves.

Each record contains relevant information about the specific characteristics of each plot, including geospatial data and information about the type of olive grove.

The plots are classified according to the Cultivation Method: Traditional/Intensive (including super-intensive) and Organic or ecological.

Traditional cultivation encompasses different planting densities (between 5 and 12 meters spacing between trees) and can have 1 to 3 tree trunks.

High-density olive groves include intensive cultivation, with tree densities exceeding 200 trees per hectare, and super-intensive cultivation surpassing 1000 trees per hectare. In these groves, various tasks are mechanized.

Both methods, traditional and intensive, often involve excessive soil tillage and compaction due to heavy machinery use, as well as the systematic application of herbicides and pesticides.

Organic olive groves are based on the premise of total soil conservation and the preservation of biological resources without the use of chemical products.

Document Content

The document is structured by countries and cultivation method, with the following records:

SPAIN		
Traditional	Intensive	Organic
ES-TD1 ES-TD5 ES-TD7 ES-TD9 ES-TD15	ES-HD2 ES-HD3 ES-HD8 ES-HD22 ES-HD40	ES-ORG4 ES-ORG6 ES-ORG11 ES-ORG12 ES-ORG13 ES-ORG14

ITALY		
Traditional	Intensive	Organic
IT-TD16 IT-TD20 IT-TD21 IT-TD50		IT-ORG17 IT-ORG18 IT-ORG19 (1-2) IT-ORG48 IT-ORG49

MOROCCO		
Traditional	Intensive	Organic
MR-TD24 MR-TD26 MR-TD27 MR-TD28 MR-TD29	MR-HD25	MR-ORG23

GREECE		
Traditional	Intensive	Organic
GR-TD30 GR-TD31 GR-TD35 GR-TD36 GR-TD37 GR-TD46	GR-HD43 GR-TD44	GR-ORG32 GR-ORG33 GR-ORG34 GR-ORG38 GR-ORG39 GR-ORG45 GR-ORG47

PORTUGAL		
Traditional	Intensive	Organic
PT-TD41	PT-HD51 PT-HD52 PT-HD53	PT-ORG42

TERMS:

Nuts: Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics

LAU: Local administrative unit

PLOTS IN SPAIN

The selected study plots in Spain are located in the southern part of the peninsula, in the autonomous community of Andalusia, specifically in the provinces of Jaén, Córdoba, and Málaga, with different cultivation systems (traditional, organic, and intensive).

SPAIN		
Traditional	Intensive	Organic
ES-TD1	ES-HD2	ES-ORG4
ES-TD5	ES-HD3	ES-ORG6
ES-TD7	ES-HD8	ES-ORG11
ES-TD9	ES-HD10	ES-ORG12
ES-TD15	ES-HD22	ES-ORG13
	ES-HD40	ES-ORG14

ES-TD1.- SPAIN Traditional

LOCATION	
Id Plot	ES-TD1
Orchard name	Las Cañadas
Cadastral ref	23075A00800213-14/23075A01100265/23075A00800201-202/23075A01100306-307-308
Country	Spain
Nuts level 2	Andalucía
Nuts level 3: Province	Jaén
LAU name	Sabiote
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	38,10078044980
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-3,22561139922

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS	
Area (ha)	102
Mean slope (%)	11.72
Mean elevation	520

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	
Olive tree variety	Picual	
Age	20	
Tree density/ha	102	
Irrigation	YES	
Organic	No	

ES-TD5.- SPAIN Traditional

LOCATION	
Id Plot	ES-TD5
Orchard name	Las Erillas
Cadastral ref	23029A05300035LX
Country	Spain (ES)
Nuts level 2	CCAA Andalucía
Nuts level 3: Province	Jaén
LAU name	Chiclana de Segura
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	38,290993
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-3,051316

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS	
Area (ha)	7,9
Mean slope (%)	16,5
Mean elevation	640

CROP CHARACTERISTICS	
Cultivation method	Traditional
Olive tree variety	Picual
Age	40
Tree density/ha	100
Number of trunks within the olive tree	2
Irrigation	NO
Organic	No

ES-TD7.- SPAIN Traditional

LOCATION	
Id Plot	ES-TD7
Orchard name	Tazaplata
Cadastral ref	23097A004004140000MF
Country	Spain (ES)
Nuts level 2	CCAA Andalucía
Nuts level 3: Province	Jaén
LAU name	Villanueva del Arzobispo
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	38,18192444260
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-3,03256387380

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS	
Area (ha)	1,1
Mean slope (%)	13
Mean elevation	661

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	
Olive tree variety	Picual	
Age	10	
Tree density/ha	100	
Number of trunks within the olive tree	2-1	
Irrigation	YES	
Organic	No	

ES-TD9.- SPAIN Traditional

LOCATION

Id Plot	ES-TD9
Orchard name	Los Robledos
Cadastral ref	23079A030000060000QZ
Country	Spain
Nuts level 2	Andalucía
Nuts level 3: Province	Jaén
LAU name	Santisteban del Puerto
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	38,18735684740
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-3,17255745234

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	49,1
Mean slope (%)	18,05
Mean elevation	595

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	
Olive tree variety	Picual	
Age	80	
Tree density/ha	100	
Irrigation	YES	
Organic	No	

ES-TD15.- SPAIN Traditional

LOCATION

Id Plot	ES-TD15
Orchard name	Pecho del Molino
Cadastral ref	14015A009000740000MP
Country	Spain
Nuts level 2	Andalucía
Nuts level 3: Province	Córdoba
LAU name	Carcabuey
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,41016509060
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-4,31590218146

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	5,3
Mean slope (%)	13,1
Mean elevation	587

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	
Olive tree variety	Hojiblanca	
Age	100	
Tree density/ha	130	
Irrigation	NO	
Organic	No	

ES-HD2.- SPAIN HIGH DENSITY		
LOCATION		
Id Plot	ES-HD2	
Orchard name	La Capilla	
Cadastral ref	29015A013000240000LD	
Country	Spain	
Nuts level 2	Andalucía	
Nuts level 3: Province	Málaga	
LAU name	Antequera	
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,19759675010	
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-4,54505908117	
<p style="text-align: center;">Coordinates GCS_WGS_1984 1:5.000</p>		
GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS		
Area (ha)	16,7	
Mean slope (%)	3-12%	
Mean elevation	491	

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Intensive	
Olive tree variety	Arbequina	
Age	7	
Tree density/ha	200-400	
Irrigation	YES	
Organic	No	

ES-HD3.- SPAIN HIGH DENSITY		
LOCATION		
Id Plot	ES-HD3	
Orchard name	Racioneros	
Cadastral ref	23100A01700094/ 23900A01800108/ 23900A01800107	
Country	Spain	
Nuts level 2	Andalucía	
Nuts level 3: Province	Jaén	
LAU name	Jaén	
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,93744223590	
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-3,62829938887	
GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS		
Area (ha)	152,3	
Mean slope (%)	3-13%	
Mean elevation	275	

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Intensive	
Olive tree variety	Sikitita	
Age	2,5	
Tree density/ha	200-400	
Irrigation	YES	
Organic	No	

ES-HD8.- SPAIN HIGH DENSITY

LOCATION

Id Plot	ES-HD8
Orchard name	El Empalme
Cadastral ref	23079A028000010000ZJ
Country	Spain
Nuts level 2	Andalucía
Nuts level 3: Province	Jaén
LAU name	Santisteban del Puerto
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	38,16525886290
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-3,15165645941

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	104,3
Mean slope (%)	19,7
Mean elevation	489

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Intensive	
Olive tree variety	Pical y Arbequina	
Age	1,5	
Tree density/ha	200-400	
Irrigation	YES	
Organic	NO	

ES-HD22.- SPAIN HIGH DENSITY

LOCATION

Id Plot	ES-HD22
Orchard name	Valdelomar
Cadastral ref	104013A002002080000GK
Country	Spain
Nuts level 2	Andalucía
Nuts level 3: Province	Córdoba
LAU name	Cabra
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,53723789610
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-4,51079030861

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	21,6
Mean slope (%)	24,8
Mean elevation	561

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Intensive	
Olive tree variety	Hojiblanca	
Age	30	
Tree density/ha	200	
Irrigation	NO	
Organic	NO	

ES-HD40.- SPAIN HIGH DENSITY

LOCATION

Id Plot	ES-HD40
Orchard name	La Dehesilla
Cadastral ref	14060A013000030000 TH
Country	Spain
Nuts level 2	Andalucía
Nuts level 3: Province	Córdoba
LAU name	Santaella
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,48300254080
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-4,84419025809

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	10,4
Mean slope (%)	12,6
Mean elevation	191

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Intensive	
Olive tree variety	Arbequina	
Age	15-25	
Tree density/ha	295	
Irrigation	YES	
Organic	No	

ES-ORG4.- SPAIN Organic

LOCATION

Id Plot	ES-ORG4
Orchard name	La Torre
Cadastral ref	29015A09100029-30/29015A09200046-47/29015A10100009-41/29015A10300001/29015A10500001
Country	Spain
Nuts level 2	Andalucía
Nuts level 3: Province	Málaga
LAU name	Antequera
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,02194580290
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-4,69454337660

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	380,3
Mean slope (%)	12
Mean elevation	447

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Hojiblanca	
Age	22	
Tree density/ha	100	
Irrigation	NO	
Organic	Yes	

ES-ORG6.- SPAIN Organic

LOCATION

Id Plot	ES-ORG6
Orchard name	El Valle
Cadastral ref	14007A00100033EQ
Country	Spain
Nuts level 2	Andalucía
Nuts level 3: Province	Córdoba
LAU name	Baena
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,79958907580
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-4,31035929087

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	3,4
Mean slope (%)	15,49
Mean elevation	351

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Picual	
Age	25	
Tree density/ha	125	
Irrigation	NO	
Organic	Yes	

ES-ORG11.- SPAIN Organic

LOCATION	
Id Plot	ES-ORG11
Orchard name	Las Parras CB
Cadastral ref	14013A010001690000GH/ 14013A010001610000GD/ 14013A010001370000GH
Country	Spain
Nuts level 2	Andalucía
Nuts level 3: Province	Córdoba
LAU name	Cabra
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,49820208150
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-4,49691899229

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS	
Area (ha)	20,1
Mean slope (%)	4,7
Mean elevation	407

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Picual	
Age	25	
Tree density/ha	180	
Irrigation	NO	
Organic	yes	

ES-ORG12.- SPAIN Organic

LOCATION

Id Plot	ES-ORG12
Orchard name	Cazorla-Las Ventas
Cadastral ref	14015A002001490000 MX
Country	Spain
Nuts level 2	Andalucía
Nuts level 3: Province	Córdoba
LAU name	Carcabuey
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,46870282710
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-4,29378895425

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	3,0
Mean slope (%)	13,1
Mean elevation	563

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Picudo	
Age	100-150	
Tree density/ha	100	
Irrigation	yes	
Organic	yes	

ES-ORG13.- SPAIN Organic

LOCATION

Id Plot	ES-ORG13
Orchard name	Oleoagro SL
Cadastral ref	14013A029000430000 GE/14013A029000420 000GJ/14013A0290 00410000G1/14013A0 29000370000GX
Country	Spain
Nuts level 2	Andalucía
Nuts level 3: Province	Córdoba
LAU name	Cabra
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,47344356100
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-4,40009613327

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	17,1
Mean slope (%)	19
Mean elevation	812

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Hojiblanca- Arduo	
Age	100-120	
Tree density/ha	80	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	Yes	

ES-ORG14.- SPAIN Organic

LOCATION

Id Plot	ES-ORG14
Orchard name	Portocarrero CB
Cadastral ref	14013A013000670000G H
Country	Spain
Nuts level 2	Andalucía
Nuts level 3: Province	Córdoba
LAU name	Cabra
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,48438429980
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-4,54808011411

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	45
Mean slope (%)	4,3
Mean elevation	352

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Hojiblanca	
Age	10-100	
Tree density/ha	50	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	yes	

PLOTS IN ITALY

The selected study plots in Italy are located in the regions of Sicily, Tuscany and Lazio, with cultivation systems traditional and organic.

ITALY	
Traditional	Organic
IT-TD16	IT-ORG17
IT-TD20	IT-ORG18
IT-TD21	IT-ORG19
IT-TD50	IT-ORG48
	IT-ORG49

IT-TD16.- ITALY Traditional

LOCATION

Id Plot	IT-TD16
Orchard name	Santa Margherita_1
Cadastral ref	Santa Margherita di Belice (AG) - Foglio di mappa 21, particella 65
Country	Italy
Nuts level 2	Isole/ Sicilia
Nuts level 3: Province	Agrigento
LAU name	Santa Margherita di Belice
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,69618082060
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	13,04779477190

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS	
Area (ha)	0,5
Mean slope (%)	5
Mean elevation	225

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	
Olive tree variety	Nocellara del Belice	
Age	25	
Tree density/ha	156	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	No	

IT-TD20.- ITALY Traditional

LOCATION

Id Plot	IT-TD20
Orchard name	Bresciana_1
Cadastral ref	Contrada Bresciano, Castelvetrano (TP). Municipal map sheet 160, various particles/plots
Country	Italy
Nuts level 2	Isole/Sicilia
Nuts level 3: Province	Trapani
LAU name	Castelvetrano
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,59605790450
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	12,78506090710

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS	
Area (ha)	1,5
Mean slope (%)	0,5
Mean elevation	32

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	
Olive tree variety	Nocellara del Belice	
Age	50-60	
Tree density/ha	200	
Irrigation	Yes	
Organic	No	

IT-TD21.- ITALY Traditional

LOCATION

Id Plot	IT-TD21
Orchard name	IAnnotta
Country	Italy
Nuts level 2	Centro (IT)/ Lazio
Nuts level 3: Province	Latina
LAU name	Sonnino
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	41,44235421440
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	13,22760177220

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	11,4
Mean slope (%)	35
Mean elevation	157

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	
Olive tree variety	Itrana	
Age	11	
Tree density/ha	250	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	No	

IT-TD50.- ITALY Traditional

LOCATION

Id Plot	IT-TD50
Orchard name	Bresciana_2
Cadastral ref	Contrada Bresciana, Castelvetrano (TP). Municipal map sheet 160
Country	Italy
Nuts level 2	Isole/Sicilia
Nuts level 3: Province	Trapani
LAU name	Castelvetrano
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,5962218490
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	12,78696025520

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS	
Area (ha)	1,7
Mean slope (%)	0,5
Mean elevation	34

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	
Olive tree variety	Nocellara del Belice	
Age	50	
Tree density/ha	150	
Irrigation	Yes	
Organic	No	

IT-ORG17.- ITALY Organic	
LOCATION	
Id Plot	IT-ORG17
Orchard name	Santa Margherita_2
Cadastral ref	Santa Margherita di Belice (AG) - Municipal map sheet 21, particle 57
Country	Italy
Nuts level 2	Isole/ Sicilia
Nuts level 3: Province	Agrigento
LAU name	Santa Margherita di Belice
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,69730706160
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	13,04620152730
GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS	
Area (ha)	0,6
Mean slope (%)	8
Mean elevation	234

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Nocellara del Belice	
Age	25	
Tree density/ha	124	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	Yes	

IT-ORG18.- ITALY Organic

LOCATION	
Id Plot	IT-ORG18
Orchard name	Seggio-Torre
Country	Italy
Nuts level 2	Isole/ Sicilia
Nuts level 3: Province	Trapani
LAU name	Castelvetrano
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,67399512910
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	12,86387416580

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	10,4
Mean slope (%)	1,5
Mean elevation	180

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Nocellara del Belice 95% Cerasuola 5%	
Age	7	
Tree density/ha	230	
Irrigation	Yes	
Organic	Yes	

IT-ORG19_1- ITALY Organic		
LOCATION		
Id Plot	IT-ORG19_1	
Orchard name	Canalotto	
Cadastral ref	Contrada Canalotto, foglio di mappa 121,part.lle 9 e 113; Contrada Seggio Torre,foglio di mappa 77, particelle 30-31-111.	
Country	Italy	
Nuts level 2	Isole/Sicilia	
Nuts level 3: Province	Trapani	
LAU name	Castelvetrano	
Latitude 19-1 (centroid) WGS84	37,63320141610	
Longitude 19-1(centroid) WGS84	12,78439572900	
<p style="text-align: right;">• Coordinates</p>		

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS 19-1	
Area (ha)	11,7
Mean slope (%)	0,8
Mean elevation	76

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Nocellara del Belice 90% Giarrappa 10%	
Age	50	
Tree density/ha	155	
Irrigation	Yes	
Organic	Yes	

IT-ORG48.- ITALY Organic		
LOCATION		
Id Plot	IT-ORG48	
Orchard name	Olivart	
Country	Italy	
Nuts level 2	Centro (IT)/ Toscana	
Nuts level 3: Province	Firenze	
LAU name	Bagno a Ripoli	
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	43,71680213350	
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	11,30900790020	
<p style="text-align: center;">● Coordinates GCS_WGS_1984 1:3.000</p>		
GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS		
Area (ha)		6,8
Mean slope (%)		13
Mean elevation		189

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Frantoio	
Age	35	
Tree density/ha	200	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	Yes	

IT-ORG49.- ITALY Organic

LOCATION

Id Plot	IT-ORG49
Orchard name	Ss_Annunziata
Cadastral ref	
Country	Italy
Nuts level 2	Centro (IT)/Toscana
Nuts level 3: Province	Livorno
LAU name	San Vincenzo
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	43,09899568340
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	10,56272256990

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	17,0
Mean slope (%)	8
Mean elevation	89

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Frantoio	
Age	80	
Tree density/ha	160	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	Yes	

PLOTS IN MOROCCO

The selected study plots in Morocco are located in the regions of Meknès, El Hajeb, Azilal and Béni Mellal, with cultivation systems traditional, organic and intensive.

MOROCCO		
Traditional	Intensive	Organic
MR-TD24	MR-HD25	MR-ORG23
MR-TD26		
MR-TD27		
MR-TD28		
MR-TD29		

MR-TD24. MOROCCO. Traditional

LOCATION

Id Plot	MR-TD24
Orchard name	Sodeom
Country	Morocco
Nuts level 2	Meknès - Tafilalet
Nuts level 3: Province	El Hajeb
LAU name	Agourai/ Jahjouh
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	33,79865892030
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-5,69271076910

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	7,9
Mean slope (%)	2-4%
Mean elevation	598

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	
Olive tree variety	Picholine marocaine	
Age	45	
Tree density/ha	204	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	No	

MR-TD26. MOROCCO. Traditional

LOCATION

Id Plot	MR-TD26
Orchard name	Sodeom 2
Country	Morocco
Nuts level 2	Meknès - Tafilalet
Nuts level 3: Province	El Hajeb
LAU name	Agourai /Ras ljerri
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	33,82204652280
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-5,69692159662

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	58,6
Mean slope (%)	2-4%
Mean elevation	556

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	
Olive tree variety	Picholine marocaine	
Age	60	
Tree density/ha	178	
Irrigation	Yes	
Organic	No	

MR-TD27. MOROCCO. Traditional

LOCATION

Id Plot	MR-TD27
Orchard name	Belhassen Ferme
Country	Morocco
Nuts level 2	Tadla - Azilal
Nuts level 3: Province	Azilal
LAU name	Demnate/ Tifni
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	31,69942206250
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-6,97220226328

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	2,3
Mean slope (%)	0
Mean elevation	1133

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	
Olive tree variety	Picholine marocaine	
Age	13	
Tree density/ha	142	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	No	

MR-TD28.- MOROCCO. Traditional

LOCATION

Id Plot	MR-HD28
Orchard name	Malak Ferme
Country	Morocco
Nuts level 2	Meknès - Tafilalet
Nuts level 3: Province	El Hajeb
LAU name	El Hajeb /Ait Bourzouine
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	33,71843871720
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-5,49449805788

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	7,1
Mean slope (%)	<1%
Mean elevation	758

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	High density	
Olive tree variety	Picholine marocaine et Menara	
Age	7	
Tree density/ha	400	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	No	

MR-TD29. MOROCCO. Traditional

LOCATION

Id Plot	MR-TD29
Orchard name	Markzen
Country	Morocco
Nuts level 2	Tadla - Azilal
Nuts level 3: Province	Béni Mellal
LAU name	Bni Moussa /Oulad Zmam
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	32,43432341710
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-6,74728199981

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	12,7
Mean slope (%)	<1%
Mean elevation	412

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	TRADITIONAL	
Olive tree variety	Picholine Marocaine	
Age	60	
Tree density/ha	100	
Irrigation	Yes	
Organic	No	

MR-HD25.- MOROCCO. Intensive

LOCATION

Id Plot	MR-HD25
Orchard name	Les Vergers de Tizguit
Country	Morocco
Nuts level 2	Meknès - Tafilalet
Nuts level 3: Province	El Hajeb
LAU name	Ain Taoujda/ Ait Boubidmane
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	33,82107563130
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-5,26058940662

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	40,6
Mean slope (%)	<1%
Mean elevation	736

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Intensive	
Olive tree variety	Arbequina	
Age	12	
Tree density/ha	1250	
Irrigation	Yes	
Organic	No	

MR-ORG23. MOROCCO. Organic

LOCATION

Id Plot	MR-ORG23
Orchard name	Domaine Amri
Country	Morocco
Nuts level 2	Meknès - Tafilalet
Nuts level 3: Province	Meknès/ Zerhoun
LAU name	Charqaoua
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	34,13702701630
Longitude(centroid) WGS84	-5,45260805540

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	38,5
Mean slope (%)	0,1
Mean elevation	300

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Picholine marocaine	
Age	55	
Tree density/ha	100	
Irrigation	Yes	
Organic	Yes	

PLOTS IN GREECE

The selected study plots in Greece are located in the regions of Peloponnese, North Aegean and Crete, with cultivation systems traditional, organic and intensive.

GREECE		
Traditional	Intensive	Organic
GR-TD30	GR-HD43	GR-ORG32
GR-TD31		GR-ORG33
GR-TD35		GR-ORG34
GR-TD36		GR-ORG38
GR-TD37		GR-ORG39
GR-TD44		GR-ORG45
GR-TD46		GR-ORG47

GR-TD30. GREECE. Traditional

LOCATION

Id Plot	GR-TD30
Orchard name	Adamopoulos farm_1
Cadastral ref	GR_KAL_TRAD_1 & GR_KAL_TRAD_2
Country	Greece
Nuts level 2	Peloponnese
Nuts level 3: Province	Laconia, Messenia
LAU name	Sterna
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,09092256340
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	21,87064286540

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	1,3
Mean slope (%)	0-5%
Mean elevation	213

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	
Olive tree variety	Koroneiki	
Age	70	
Tree density/ha	200	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	No	

GR-TD31. GREECE. Traditional

LOCATION

Id Plot	GR-TD31
Orchard name	Adamopoulos Farm_2
Cadastral ref	Gr_Kal_Trad_1 & Gr_Kal_Trad_2
Country	Greece
Nuts level 2	Peloponnese
Nuts level 3: Province	Laconia, Messenia
LAU name	Sterna
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,09926421170
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	21,85329973650

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	1,2
Mean slope (%)	5-10%
Mean elevation	310

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	
Olive tree variety	Koroneiki	
Age	70	
Tree density/ha	200	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	No	

GR-TD35. GREECE. Traditional

LOCATION

Id Plot	GR-TD35
Orchard name	Kalamitsi
Cadastral ref	G-So-5
Country	Greece
Nuts level 2	North Aegean
Nuts level 3: Province	Lesbos
LAU name	Paleokipos
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	39,05981268310
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	26,45930451640

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	0,5
Mean slope (%)	18
Mean elevation	75-97

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	olive trees photo
Olive tree variety	Kolovi	
Age	100	
Tree density/ha	175	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	No	

GR-TD36. GREECE. Traditional

LOCATION

Id Plot	GR-TD36
Orchard name	Nitsa
Cadastral ref	G-So-4
Country	Greece
Nuts level 2	North Aegean
Nuts level 3: Province	Lesbos
LAU name	Messagros
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	39,04202200650
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	26,43819013450

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	1,2
Mean slope (%)	6
Mean elevation	178-216

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	olive trees photo
Olive tree variety	Kolovi (85%), Adramitini (6,5%), Ladolia (6%), Koroneiki (2,5%)	
Age	70	
Tree density/ha	266	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	No	

GR-TD37. GREECE. Traditional

LOCATION

Id Plot	GR-TD37
Orchard name	Kiria
Cadastral ref	G-So-3
Country	Greece
Nuts level 2	North Aegean
Nuts level 3: Province	Lesbos
LAU name	Pappados
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	39,04574202790
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	26,48382321540

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	0,2
Mean slope (%)	3
Mean elevation	21

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	
Olive tree variety	Kolov	
Age	100	
Tree density/ha	160	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	No	

GR-TD44. GREECE. Intensive

LOCATION

Id Plot	GR-TD44
Orchard name	5C (Plakoyres 1)
Country	Greece
Nuts level 2	Crete
Nuts level 3: Province	Heraklion
LAU name	Siva
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	35,03192321260
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	24,80931256440

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	0,3
Mean slope (%)	0-5%
Mean elevation	74

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	
Olive tree variety	Koroneiki	
Age	40	
Tree density/ha	200	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	No	

GR-TD46. GREECE. Traditional

LOCATION

Id Plot	GR-TD46
Orchard name	10C (Aygerinos 1)
Country	Greece
Nuts level 2	Crete
Nuts level 3: Province	Heraklion
LAU name	Pobia
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	35,03602734370
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	24,85153851790

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	1,4
Mean slope (%)	0
Mean elevation	50

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	
Olive tree variety	Koroneiki	
Age	40	
Tree density/ha	200	
Irrigation	Yes	
Organic	No	

GR-HD43. GREECE. Intensive

LOCATION

Id Plot	GR-HD43
Orchard name	6C (Paliomandres)
Country	Greece
Nuts level 2	Crete
Nuts level 3: Province	Heraklion
LAU name	Siva
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	35,00767637750
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	24,80203619190

Coordinates GCS_WGS_1984 1:1.300

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	1,1
Mean slope (%)	0
Mean elevation	97

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Intensive	
Olive tree variety	Koroneiki	
Age	4	
Tree density/ha	200-400	
Irrigation	Yes	
Organic	No	

GR-ORG32. GREECE. Organic

LOCATION

Id Plot	GR-ORG32
Orchard name	Lieas
Cadastral ref	Gr_Kal_Org_3
Country	Greece
Nuts level 2	Peloponnese
Nuts level 3: Province	Laconia, Messenia
LAU name	Avramio
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,03987759250
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	21,94789857760

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	1,0
Mean slope (%)	0
Mean elevation	90

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Koroneiki	
Age	10-150	
Tree density/ha	180	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	Yes	

GR-ORG33. GREECE. Organic

LOCATION

Id Plot	GR-ORG33
Orchard name	Draina
Cadastral ref	Gr_Kal_Org_1
Country	Greece
Nuts level 2	Peloponnese
Nuts level 3: Province	Laconia, Messenia
LAU name	Draina
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,10912383760
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	21,86257457190

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	1,3
Mean slope (%)	15
Mean elevation	290

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Koroneiki	
Age	10-300	
Tree density/ha	150	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	Yes	

GR-ORG34. GREECE. Organic

LOCATION

Id Plot	GR-ORG34
Orchard name	Sterna
Cadastral ref	Gr_Kal_Org_2
Country	Greece
Nuts level 2	Peloponnese
Nuts level 3: Province	Laconia, Messenia
LAU name	Sterna
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	37,07765646180
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	21,88032249380

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	0,6
Mean slope (%)	10
Mean elevation	203

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Koroneiki	
Age	40	
Tree density/ha	170	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	Yes	

GR-ORG38. GREECE. Organic

LOCATION

Id Plot	GR-ORG38
Orchard name	Paspalas
Cadastral ref	G-So-2
Country	Greece
Nuts level 2	North Aegean
Nuts level 3: Province	Lesbos
LAU name	Komi
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	39,19696685770
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	26,40044615950

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	11,5
Mean slope (%)	0
Mean elevation	202-293

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Adramitini (80%), Kolovi (20%)	
Age	15-100	
Tree density/ha	265	
Irrigation	Yes	
Organic	Yes	

GR-ORG39. GREECE. Organic

LOCATION

Id Plot	GR-ORG39
Orchard name	Briani
Cadastral ref	G-So-1
Country	Greece
Nuts level 2	North Aegean
Nuts level 3: Province	Lesbos
LAU name	Skopelos
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	38,99520222020
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	26,46632243910

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	1,6
Mean slope (%)	0
Mean elevation	307-342

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Kolovi	
Age	100	
Tree density/ha	260	
Irrigation	No	
Organic	Yes	

GR-ORG45. GREECE. Organic

LOCATION

Id Plot	GR-ORG45
Orchard name	90 (Mandres)
Country	Greece
Nuts level 2	Crete
Nuts level 3: Province	Heraklion
LAU name	Mires
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	35,06838348160
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	24,90069156510

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	2,1
Mean slope (%)	5-10%
Mean elevation	265

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Koroneki / Throubolia	
Age	60	
Tree density/ha	150	
Irrigation	Yes	
Organic	Yes	

GR-ORG47. GREECE. Organic

LOCATION

Id Plot	GR-ORG47
Orchard name	100 (Aygerinos 2)
Country	Greece
Nuts level 2	Crete
Nuts level 3: Province	Heraklion
LAU name	Pobia
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	35,03593291010
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	24,84811048700

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	0,5
Mean slope (%)	0
Mean elevation	48

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Koroneiki	
Age	40	
Tree density/ha	200	
Irrigation	Yes	
Organic	Yes	

PLOTS IN PORTUGAL

The selected study plots in Morocco are located in the regions of Beja and Bragança and cultivation systems: traditional, organic and intensive.

PORTUGAL		
Traditional	Intensive	Organic
PT-TD41	PT-HD51 PT-HD52 PT-HD53	PT-ORG42

PT-TD41. PORTUGAL. Traditional		
LOCATION		
Id Plot	PT-TD41	
Orchard name	Ujeira	
Country	Portugal	
Nuts level 2	Norte	
Nuts level 3: Province	Douro	
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	41.531	
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-7.0471	
GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS		
Area (ha)		2
Mean slope (%)		9
Mean elevation		527

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Traditional	
Olive tree variety	Cobrançosa	
Age	30	
Tree density/ha	278	
Irrigation	Yes	
Organic	No	

PT-HD51. PORTUGAL. Intensive

LOCATION

Id Plot	PT-HD51	
Orchard name	Olivadouro	
Country	Portugal	
Nuts level 2	Norte	
Nuts level 3: Province	Douro	
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	41.2417	
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-7.1027	

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	43
Mean slope (%)	2
Mean elevation	130

CROP CHARACTERISTICS

Cultivation method	High density	
Olive tree variety	Arbequina	
Age	10	
Tree density/ha	800	
Irrigation	Yes	
Organic	No	

PT-HD52. PORTUGAL. Intensive

LOCATION

Id Plot	PT-HD52
Orchard name	HERDADE DOS PATOS
Country	Portugal
Nuts level 2	Continente/ALENTEJO
Nuts level 3: Province	Beja
LAU name	Alvito
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	38,15942950980
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-8,06561485622

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	676,8
Mean slope (%)	2
Mean elevation	114

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Intensive	
Olive tree variety	Arbequina/Arbosana	
Age	7	
Tree density/ha	1852	
Irrigation	Yes	
Organic	no	

PT-HD53.- PORTUGAL. Intensive

LOCATION

Id Plot	PT-HD53
Orchard name	HERDADE QUINTA DA CHAMINE
Country	Portugal
Nuts level 2	Continente/ ALENTEJO
Nuts level 3: Province	Beja
LAU name	Ferreira do Alentejo
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	38,02600980360
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-8,12035507123

GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Area (ha)	402,8
Mean slope (%)	0.5
Mean elevation	120

CROP CHARACTERISTICS	
Cultivation method	intensive
Olive tree variety	Arbequina/Arbosana
Age	6
Tree density/ha	1852
Irrigation	Yes
Organic	No

PT-ORG42. PORTUGAL. Organic		
LOCATION		
Id Plot	PT-ORG42	
Orchard name	Azinha Cova	
Country	Portugal	
Nuts level 2	Norte	
Nuts level 3: Province	Douro	
Latitude (centroid) WGS84	41.3329	
Longitude (centroid) WGS84	-7.042	
GEOGRAPHICAL CHARACTERISTICS		
Area (ha)		6
Mean slope (%)		1
Mean elevation		242

CROP CHARACTERISTICS		
Cultivation method	Organic	
Olive tree variety	Cobrançosa	
Age	25	
Tree density/ha	225	
Irrigation	Yes	
Organic	Yes	

Annex 2. FAIR data principles

It must be met that the data resulting from the investigation is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), to ensure that it is managed correctly.

To be **Findable**:

- F1.** (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- F2.** data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
- F3.** metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
- F4.** (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

To be **Accessible**:

- A1.** (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
 - A1.1** the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
 - A1.2** the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
- A2.** metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

To be **Interoperable**:

- I1.** (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- I2.** (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
- I3.** (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

To be **Reusable**:

- R1.** meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
 - R1.1.** (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
 - R1.2.** (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
 - R1.3.** (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

(Mark D. Wilkinson et al. 2016)

Annex 3. General metadata Soil O-live project

DATA IDENTIFICATION

Resource title: SOIL O-LIVE

Resource abstract:

After more than fifty years of intensive agriculture application, the environmental situation for many olive groves across the Mediterranean Region is quite dramatic in terms of land degradation, biodiversity impoverishment, functionality loss, which may have already impacted on the quality and safety of olive oil, one of the most important commodities produced in Europe. Through the implementation of a series of multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary WPs, this project will perform the first rigorous diagnostic of the environmental situation of olive groves soils at a broad scale, considering the most important areas of olive production at the Mediterranean Region and its relationships to olive oil quality. Soil O-live aims (i) to analyze the impact of pollution and land degradation on soils from olive groves in terms of multi-biodiversity, ecological function at different levels of organization and scales; (ii) to investigate the relationship of soil health status with quality and safety of olive oil; (iii) to implement effective soil amendments and ecological restoration practices that promote manifest soil biodiversity and functionality enhancements in permanent Mediterranean olive orchards across its native range of distribution, that should be translated to improvements in olive oil quality and safety; (iv) to define rigorous ecological thresholds that allow to implement future clear norms and regulations in order to design a novel certification for healthy soils in European olive orchards.

More information about the SOIL O-LIVE (methodology and classification) can be found at the <http://xxxxxxxxxx>

Resource type: Dataset

Resource Locator: <http://zenodoxxxxxxxx>

Topic of category: HORIZON-MISS-2021-SOIL-02-03

Type of action: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions

Granting authority: European Research Executive Agency

Keyword: Agricultural engineering, food safety, – Soil conservation, – Soil functions, – Soil pollution
Wilkinson

GEOGRAPHIC REFERENCE

Bounding Box:

North: 45,9295

South: 30,3678

East: 27,8118

West: -9,7361

Coverage: Greece, Italy, Morocco, Portugal, Spain,

Geotags: Olive grove areas in Greece, Italy, Morocco, Portugal, Spain

Coordinate Reference System:

EPSG4326

Datum: D_WGS_1984

TEMPORAL REFERENCE

Temporal extent:

Project starting date: fixed date: 1 January 2023

Project end date: 31 December 2027

Date of publication: Xx/xx/xxx

QUALITY AND VALIDITY

Lineage:

1. Microdata

The environmental parameters associated with the individual measured points are freely available for download at xxxxxxxx.

Soil results for the 5 countries are available through the JRC land resources management unit under license agreement.

2. Images

Point and landscape photos taken in the four cardinal directions at each point are freely available upon request by email to xxx@xxxxx or via the online order form.

3. Statistical tables

Statistical tables with results are available at xxxxxxxx. Also, there are tables with xxxxxxxx data.

CONSTRAINTS RELATED TO ACCESS AND USE

Conditions applying to access and use²:

SOIL O-LIVE data is free and open to the public

Limitation of public access³:

No Limitation

RESPONSIBLE ORGANISATION

Responsible party⁴:

European Research Executive Agency (REA)(1), University of Jaen (UJAEN) (2), etc.....

Responsible party role⁵:

- (1) Granting authority
- (2) Coordinator

Other organizations involved in the project (Beneficiaries):

- UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI ROMA TRE
- FREIE UNIVERSITAET BERLIN
- UNIVERSIDAD DE CASTILLA - LA MANCHA
- PANEPISTIMIO AIGAIUO
- AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE
- INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS
- UNIVERSIDADE DE TRAS-OS-MONTES E ALTO DOURO
- ASOCIACION ESPANOLA DE NORMALIZACION
- ELLINIKO MESOGEIAKO PANEPISTIMIO

² Restriction on the access and use of a resource or metadata

³ Limitation and other reason for public access

⁴ Organization associated with the resource. Organization name, contact information (email)

⁵ Function performed by the party

- NUTESCA SL
- ELLINIKOS GEORGIKOS ORGANISMOS - DIMITRA
- UNIWERSYTET SLASKI W KATOWICACH
- UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI PALERMO
- CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE
- ECOLE NATIONALE D'AGRICULTURE DE MEKNES
- DEOLEO GLOBAL SA

Associated partners: UNIVERSITAT BASEL

Annex 4. MORPHO guide: creating metadata with MORPHO

Morpho

Morpho is an application to facilitate the creation of metadata and data sets.

Metadata:

The metadata contains information about the content of a data set (its owner, administrator, geographic extent, units, etc.) as well as who has access to the data (the owner, selected users, or the public). The metadata file is stored on your local system and/or on the KNB network. Metadata can be "packaged" with the data set, or can stand alone much like an abstract describing the contents of a paper.

Data packages:

Data packages are the logical units that Morpho creates to represent a collection of metadata and (optionally) data files. At its most basic, a data package consists only of high-level documentation: metadata about a data collection's title and abstract, keywords, people and organizations, usage rights, research project information, coverage details, methods and sampling, and access information. Once a basic data package has been created, you can add metadata for the individual data tables (row and column information) and optionally include the data tables themselves in the package.

Downloading and Installing Morpho

To download Morpho, go to <http://knb.ecoinformatics.org/morphoportal.jsp> and choose the link corresponding to your platform (Morpho can be used on Windows, Linux, and Mac). You will need to have Java 1.6 or later installed on your system.

Morpho will be installed in one of the following languages (English, French, Spanish and Portuguese), depending on the language in which your operating system is installed

Before you Begin

1.-Create a User Profile

Morpho interacts with the Knowledge Network for Biocomplexity (KNB) Metacat server. But the **Soil O-Live** project will use the **ZENODO data repository**, so **you don't need to register** and dump the data into KNB.

The metadata and the data package (tables, documents, images) must be saved in your local storage and sent to sig_soilolive@ujaen.es (**Zip Format**)

Attention: you don't need to register and dump the data into KNB.

On the "Basic Information" screen of the New Profile wizard, enter your profile name and your first and last name.

w profile... ✕

Enter the name for this profile and your first and last name.

New profile...

Basic Information

Name of profile:

First Name:

Last Name:

New profile... ✕

Enter the information you submitted when you registered for the Knowledge Network for Biocomplexity (KNB). If you have not registered for the KNB yet, go to: <http://knb.ecoinformatics.org/> This will allow you to login to the network and collaborate with other researchers through the KNB.

New profile...

Network Account Information

Username:

Organization:

PISCOGROUPS
unaffiliated
NCEAS

Refresh:

New profile... ✕

Enter a short identifier prefix for this profile. All data packages you create under this profile will bear this identifier prefix. For example, using the prefix 'jane_doe', data packages will have names like jane_doe.1.1, jane_doe.2.1, etc.

New profile...

Data Package Identification

Identifier prefix:

Note: Please do not use "temporary" because it is a reserved word.
Illegal characters: '!', '&', '#', '!', '!', '+', '!', '!', '!'

The identifier prefix will be used to create IDs for metadata documents you create in Morpho, and for data tables or other data files you import using Morpho. For example, specifying the prefix "AJM" will result in document IDs like AJM.1.1, AJM.2.1, etc.

2.-Creating a Data Package

When you create a data package in Morpho, you begin by entering data about the entire data set (e.g., title, abstract, and contact information). This summary information is the *minimum* amount of documentation necessary for creating a data package.

Once the entire data set has been described using the Data Package wizard, you can begin adding information about the data objects them-selves (i.e., information about the individual data tables, such as column names and measurement scales).

3.- Adding Metadata to the Package

The Data Package wizard helps you gather the minimum amount of documentation necessary for creating a data package:

- Title and Abstract
- Keywords
- People and Organizations
- Research Project Information
- Usage Rights
- Coverage Details (geographic, temporal, taxonomic)
- Methods and Sampling
- Access Information
- Summary

Required fields are identified with red labels. You must fill out all re-quired fields before proceeding to the next step. Remember, you can al-ways change the documentation at a later time using items in the **Documentation menu**.

The wizard displays instructions for filling out each screen. We recommend that you read the explanatory text before filling out the wizard forms.

Title and Abstract

The second step of the Data Package Wizard collects a data set title (required) and abstract. The title provides a full description of the package, and should be detailed enough to differentiate the package from

New Data Package Wizard

Title and Abstract

Enter the title of the data that is long enough to differentiate it from other similar data.
e.g. Vernal Pool Amphibian Density Data, Isla Vista, CA USA, 1990-1996

Title: Population sampling data for zooplankton in the Great Lakes, 2000

Enter an abstract that describes the data package. This abstract is a paragraph or more that describes the particular data that are being documented. You may want to describe the objectives, key aspects, design or methods of the study.

Population sampling data for various zooplankton species in the Great Lakes, 2000. Sampling used Van Dorn samples at 1 m and 5 m depths on a randomly placed sampling grid. Species names according to the ITS taxonomic database | (<http://www.its.usda.gov/>).

Abstract:

Save for Later Step 2 of 15 Cancel < Back Next > Finish

Keywords

Keywords – significant words or phrases that help identify the data set. To add a new set of keywords, click “Add” to open the “Define Keyword Set” screen. Click the “Add” button on the Define Keyword Set screen to add a keyword to the list.

People and Organizations:

There are three types of people to document:

Owner (*required*) The person(s) or organization(s) credited with creating the data (e.g., a principal investigator)

Contact (*required*) The person(s) or organization(s) to contact with questions about use or interpretation of the data. The contact may be the same as the owner.

Associated parties (*optional*) People or organizations functionally associated with the data. For example, the person who maintains the database is an associated party with the role of 'custodian'.

New Data Package Wizard

People or Organizations Associated With This Data Package

Owners

Enter information about the Owners. This is information about the persons or organizations certified as data owners (e.g. the principal investigator(s) of the project). The list of data owners should include all people and organizations who should be cited for the data. Select Add to add an owner.

One or more Owners must be defined:

Party	Role	Address	
Dr. Jone Scientist	Owner	Marine Science Institute	<input type="button" value="Add"/> <input type="button" value="Edit"/> <input type="button" value="Delete"/> <input type="button" value="Move Up"/> <input type="button" value="Move Do..."/>

Save for Later Step 5 of 15 Cancel < Back Next > Finish

Owner Details

Chose to populate the fields using information from a previously entered owner, or from an owner specified in another data package.

You can pick from one of the earlier entries that you have made.

Salutation:

First Name:

Last Name:

Organization:

Position Name:

Address 1:

Address 2:

City: State:

Postal Code: Country:

Phone: Fax:

Email: Online URL:

OK Cancel

Research Project Information

Data may be associated with a single, independent investigation, or they may be collected as part of a research program with many sub-projects. If your data is part of a larger research project, indicate this by marking the checkbox. You will be prompted to enter the name of the larger project, its funding source, and one or more associated people or organizations.

Usage Rights

Specify the intended usage rights and restrictions (scientific, technical, ethical) for sharing your data within the public domain. You may request that users inform the contact person if they wish to use the data package, for example, or that they read use and access policies that are posted on a website.

Coverage Details (geographic, temporal, taxonomic)

Coverage can be a single point or a region. After you click the Add button, the Geographic Coverage details screen opens. A textual description of the spatial coverage is required. In addition, you must specify coverage coordinates.

Specify temporal coverage details

Specify taxonomic coverage (optional)

Enter information about the Taxonomic Coverage. By default, you may enter information on Genus and Species. If you would like to enter information at another classification rank or would like to change the default classification rank, click the edit button. Note that the field 'Higher Level Taxa' is dynamically generated from your entries and is not manually editable.

If your information about the taxonomic coverage is extensive (e.g., an extensive list of species), you can import this information. See the Frequently Asked Questions section of the Morpho User Guide to find out how to do this.

Higher Level Taxa	Rank	Name	Rank	Name	Common Name(s)	
	Genus	Gaultheria	Species	procumbens	winterberry	Add
	Genus		Species			Edit
						Delete

Classification System If the list of taxa belong to one or more different classification systems, list the citations for those systems.

Citation Title	Creator	Citation Type	
			Add
			Edit
			Delete

Annotations:
 - Click Add to add additional taxonomic records.
 - Click a blank field to enter a value.
 - Click Edit to change the default classification rank (e.g., to specify a family name).

Enter the Taxonomic Hierarchy (in descending order):

Rank	Name	Common Name(s)
Kingdom		
Phylum		
Class		
Order		
Family	Ericaceae	
Genus	Gaultheria	
Species	procumbens	winterberry

Buttons: Add, Delete, Move Up, Move Down, OK, Cancel

Entering the taxonomic hierarchy (for more than two levels).

Methods and Sampling

Method and sampling information describes the steps followed in implementing an experiment and the experiment’s sampling design. Although this information is not required, it helps other users understand your data and how it was assembled. To add a method description, click “Add” to open the Step Information screen).

Enter a method title (optional), description (required), and instrumentation details (optional), then click “OK” to return to the main Methods and Sampling screen.

Study extent information supplements the information already provided in the temporal or spatial extent of the study.

Use the sampling description field to provide details on the sampling design of the study.

Access Information

By setting access information, you control who has access to your data and metadata. For example, you can specify that the public can view your data, or that only specified colleagues can do so.

By default, the settings specified in the wizard apply to all metadata and data tables imported into the package. However, after you have added one or more data tables to the package, you can choose to set different permissions for each table using the “Edit Data Table Access” option in the Data menu.

Summary

Your data package will be created when you click Finish. Please note that you must save the package or the information entered will be lost. Once the data package is created, it is already possible to add tables or other information.

Click Finish to view the data package documentation, or click the "or click to finish this wizard and add a new data table now" link to add a data table to the package immediately.

If you haven't saved your package yet (File > Save), Morpho

will prompt you to save the package before closing it. You can choose to save the package locally or on the network. **You must save it locally.**

Saving Incomplete Data Packages

You can save incomplete data packages. Click the "Save for later" button at any step and the incomplete data packet will be saved locally. The incomplete data pack can be opened like any other data pack from the open menu option.

Adding Data to the Data Package

Data documentation describes the data object – the columns and rows, the units used, etc. In this section we will look at how to add data and data documentation to a package using the Data Table wizard.

Opening the Data Table Wizard

The Data Table wizard helps users add data and data documentation to a data package. The wizard steps through the process of importing data (or manually creating it) and adding the proper documentation. Note that you must complete the wizard. If you exit before finishing, you will lose your changes.

Users can choose to import an existing data table and (optionally) extract metadata from it, or to document a data table without including the data set itself in the package.

Fields labeled in red are required, and you cannot proceed to the next step without first specifying the required values

Open a data package and select Create, Import, or Describe the data object

Create

Document and then create a data table from scratch, populating it using Morpho's spreadsheet-style data editor.

If your data table does not yet exist, you may wish to create both the documentation and data table using Morpho.

Import

Import a data table and (optionally) automatically extract documentation from the data table to use in the metadata.

When you choose to import a data file, Morpho will locate the file on your computer, guide you through the documentation process, and include the file as part of the data package. If your data set exists as a delimited text file, you can instruct Morpho to automatically extract certain documentation from the data file (in which case, Morpho will extract table headers and other information contained in the table and prepopulate the corresponding wizard fields with information.

Describe

If you choose to describe your data, the Data Table wizard will step you through the process of providing documentation for it.

Documenting the Data Table

The first few screens of the Data Table wizard collect Data File Information, Data Table Information, and Data Attribute Information.

Data File Information

Once you have selected how you would like to add a data table to the package (by creating, importing, or describing it), the Data Table wizard requests information about the format of the data file.

The instructions in this section are for working with tabular data (for example, simple delimited text).

For more information on working with non-text files or see Adding other types of data tables.

After selecting a data file format, the data table wizard prompts for additional details about that format

If you're importing a data file and don't know which delimiter it uses, open the file and check how the table values are separated. You must also specify whether the attributes are arranged in columns (that is, headers are located at the top of the table) or rows (that is, headers are located on the left side of the table).

Data Table Information

Data packages may contain any number of data tables. In order to clearly identify each, the Data Table wizard prompts you to specify a table name, description, and attribute documentation

A table name is required, as well as at least one attribute definition (we recommend that you document all attributes). The table name is used to identify the table, and should be short but still uniquely identify the table. An attribute is usually a column of the data table, such as date

or site. For example, a definition for a site attribute would clarify what the values mean

New Data Table Wizard

Data File Information:

File Format

Enter some information about your data file.

What is the format of your data?

- Simple delimited text format (uses one or more delimiters throughout the file).
- Complex text format (delimited fields, fixed width fields, and mixtures of the two).
- Non-text or proprietary formatted file that is externally defined (e.g. Microsoft Excel).

Simple delimited text format (uses one or more delimiters throughout the file).

Data Attributes are arranged in:

- Columns
- Rows

Define one or more delimiters used to indicate the ends of fields:

Delimiter(s)

- tab
- comma
- space
- semicolon
- other

Buttons: Save for Later, Cancel, < Back, Next >, Finish

New Data Table Wizard

Data Information:

Table (Entity)

Enter some information about the data table contained in your file. If you have more than one data table, additional tables may be added after the completion of this wizard.

Table name: **A table name is required.**

Enter a paragraph that describes the table or entity, its type, and relevant information about the data that it contains.
[Example: Species abundance data for 1996 at the VCR LTER site]

Description:

One or more attributes (columns) must be defined.

Attribute Name	Attribute Definition	Measurement Scale

Attributes

Buttons: Add, Edit, Delete, Move Up, Move Down

Buttons: Save for Later, Cancel, < Back, Next >, Finish

Click Add to describe each table attribute (e.g., a column of the data table, such as date or site).

Though a table description is not required, we recommend that you briefly describe the table and provide information about the data it contains to document the overall meaning of the table. Click the Add button to open the Define Attribute screen and begin documenting the table attributes

Define Attribute or Column:

Name: Name of the attribute as it appears in the data file

Label: A more readable label for the attribute

Definition: Define the contents of the attribute (or column) precisely, so that a data user could interpret the attribute accurately.
e.g. "spden" is the number of individuals of all macro invertebrate species found in the plot

Storage: Storage type for this field e.g. integer, float

Storage System: The system used to define the storage types e.g. C, Java, Oracle

Category:

Unordered: unordered categories or text (statistically **nominal**) e.g. Male, Female

Ordered: ordered categories (statistically **ordinal**) e.g. Low, High

Relative: values from a scale with equidistant points (statistically **interval**) e.g. 12.2 meters

Absolute: measurement scale with a meaningful zero point (statistically **ratio**) e.g. 273 Kelvin

Date-Time: date or time values from the Gregorian calendar e.g. 2002-10-24

[Help](#)

OK Cancel

Data Attribute Information

Specifying data attribute information helps you and other people using your data interpret the data accurately. For example, if a column of data is titled “spden” – a term that might be familiar to your research team, but not other scientists who may later join it (or view your data on the network) – you can clarify the meaning when you define the table attributes. For each attribute (i.e., column of data), you have an opportunity to document the name as it appears in the data table, a label that may more clearly reflect the value, a definition that further elucidates the meaning of the value, storage information, and category information. Category information, which documents the attribute’s measurement scale, is required.

Name, Label, and Definition

The Name, Label, and Definition fields identify the name and contents of the data column. The Name field is required. If you are importing a data table that contains a header row, the value should match the headers used in the data file. Morpho will detect the headers if you chose to extract metadata automatically, otherwise you will have to enter the names manually. If you are creating a data table, the name value will be used to identify the data column. The Label field is optional, but we recommend that you specify a more readable column name if the original name is difficult to interpret. The Definition, which is also required, further clarifies the meaning of the data column. The Definition is probably the most important part of defining the attribute because it provides information that helps future data users understand what the attribute means or represents.

Define Attribute or Column:

Name: Q1A Name of the attribute as it appears in the data file

Label: Habitat Plan A more readable label for the attribute

Definition: Name, Permit Number, County and State of Habitat Conservation Plan Define the contents of the attribute (or column) precisely, so that a data user could interpret the attribute accurately.
e.g.: "spden" is the number of individuals of all macro invertebrate species found in the plot

Storage: Storage type for this field e.g.: integer, float

Storage and Storage System

The Storage and Storage System fields help identify the structural type of the column values. Though not required, specifying this information helps data users know how your data are stored. Some common types include string, Boolean, integer, float, long, double, matrix, object, scalar, and array.

Category

Categories describe how the data are measured, what measurement scale they use, and how values are enumerated and defined on that scale. Selecting the proper measurement scale is critical because the scale determines the types of statistics you can use to analyze your data. The measurement scale also dictates the type of metadata needed to describe your data set (for example, categorical data never have a “unit” of measurement). When you select a category, the Data Table wizard automatically prompts you to enter only the relevant information. After you have chosen a category, the Data Table wizard prompts you to describe the units, number types, and other details about the categories themselves.

Unordered (nominal) The unordered, or nominal, scale places values into named categories. The different values within a set are unordered. Some examples of unordered scales include gender (Male/Female) and marital status (single/married/divorced). Text fields (e.g., names of study sites or U.S. telephone numbers) should be classified as nominal. When “Unordered” is chosen, the Data Table wizard prompts you to choose whether the values are “enumerated values belonging to a predefined list” (e.g., single/married/divorced), or if they are “text values.” Text values can be free-form or can match a pattern that is specified in the wizard as well.

If you choose “Enumerated values,” you will be required to define the code used by the values so that users know what each represents (e.g., M=“male”; F=“female”, etc.).

Category	Description
Unordered (nominal)	The unordered, or nominal, scale places values into named categories. The different values within a set are unordered. Some examples of unordered scales include gender (Male/Female) and marital status (single/married/divorced). Text fields should be classified as nominal.

Category	Description
Ordered (ordinal)	The ordered, or ordinal, scale places values in a set order. Ordinal data show a particular value's position relative to other values, such as "low, medium, high, etc." Some examples of ordered scales include level of agreement (Strongly agree, Agree, Disagree, Strongly disagree), or age class (Juvenile, Sub-adult, Adult).
Relative (interval)	The relative, or interval, scale uses a measurement scale of equal-sized units (e.g., degrees Celsius). The scale starts from an arbitrary point (not a meaningful zero), and so there is no concept of 'zero' of the measured quantity. Consequently, ratios of relative values are not meaningful. Some examples of relative scales include the Celsius temperature scale and the Fahrenheit temperature scale.
Absolute (ratio)	The absolute, or ratio, scale is an interval scale with a meaningful zero point. The ratio scale begins at a true zero point that represents an absolute lack of the quality being measured. Thus, ratios of values are meaningful. Examples of absolute, or ratio, scales include elevation (measured from sea-level), height, and the Kelvin temperature scale.
Date-Time	Examples of date-time values are '2003-05-05', '1999/10/10', and '2001-10-10T14:23:20.3'.

The screenshot shows a wizard interface for defining an attribute. It includes the following elements:

- Category:** A list of radio buttons for selecting the scale type:
 - Unordered: unordered categories or text (statistically **nominal**) e.g. Male, Female
 - Ordered: ordered categories (statistically **ordinal**) e.g. Low, High
 - Relative: values from a scale with equidistant points (statistically **interval**) e.g. 12.2 meters
 - Absolute: measurement scale with a meaningful zero point (statistically **ratio**) e.g. 273 Kelvin
 - Date-Time: date or time values from the Gregorian calendar e.g. 2002-10-24
- Unordered:** A section with a "Choose:" dropdown set to "Enumerated values (belong to predefined list)" and a "Location:" dropdown set to "Codes are defined here".
- Definitions:** A table with two columns: "Code" and "Definition".

Code	Definition
M	male
F	female
- Buttons:** "Add" and "Delete" buttons are located to the right of the definitions table.
- Help:** A yellow box with the text "Click Add and then click a blank row to add a Code and its Definition." has an arrow pointing to the "Add" button.
- Checkbox:** A checkbox at the bottom is labeled "Attribute contains free-text in addition to those values listed above".

Select "Codes are defined here" as the Location setting to define codes in the wizard.

Category:
 Unordered: unordered categories or text (statistically **nominal**) e.g. Male, Female
 Ordered: ordered categories (statistically **ordinal**) e.g. Low, High
 Relative: values from a scale with equidistant points (statistically **interval**) e.g. 12.2 meters
 Absolute: measurement scale with a meaningful zero point (statistically **ratio**) e.g. 273 Kelvin
 Date-Time: date or time values from the Gregorian calendar e.g. 2002-10-24

Unordered
 Choose: Enumerated values (belong to predefined list) Describe any codes that are used as values of the attribute.
 Location: Codes are imported from another table Table Name: --select table-- locate

Definitions:
 Code Definition

Attribute contains free-text in addition to those values listed above

Select “Codes are imported from another table” under the Location setting to select code definitions from the imported data table (or to import the definition table later).

Select one of the following
 Import the definitions table into Morpho later
 The definitions table has already been included in this package

Select the two columns that define the codes and definitions. The selected columns must be in the same data table.

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ExampleData...	ExampleData...	ExampleData...	ExampleData...
lake	site (Code)	sampdate	depth

Lake Erie N1 10JUN2000 1 10 Daphnia p
 Lake Erie N1 10JUN2000 5 10 Daphnia p
 Lake Erie N2 10JUN2000 1 10 Daphnia p
 Lake Erie N2 10JUN2000 5 10 Daphnia p
 Lake Erie N2 10JUN2000 1 10 Daphnia p
 Lake Erie N2 10JUN2000 5 10 Daphnia r
 Lake Erie N2 10JUN2000 1 10 Daphnia r
 Lake Erie N2 10JUN2000 5 10 Daphnia r
 Lake Erie N3 10JUN2000 1 10 Daphnia r

Is this a Code or Definition?
 Code
 Definition

If the data in the attribute or column are unordered text values, choose “Unordered” from the “Category” list, and choose “Text values (free-form or matching a pattern)” from the drop-down menu next to “Choose”. The wizard prompts you to define the text values, and provide the name of their source, if applicable.

Ordered (ordinal) Ordered data show a particular value’s position relative to other values, such as “low, medium, high.” The ordinal scale does not indicate the distance between each item. Examples of ordered scales include level of agreement (Strongly agree, Agree, Disagree, Strongly disagree), or age class (Adult, Sub-adult, Juvenile).

If the data column contains data measured on an ordered scale, select “Ordered” as the attribute category. The user interface for defining ordered values is the same as the one for defining unordered values.

Relative (interval) Relative (interval) The relative, or interval, scale uses a measurement scale of equal-sized units (e.g., degrees Celsius). The scale starts from an arbitrary point (not a meaningful zero), and so there is no concept of 'zero' of the measured quantity.

You can define a new unit to represent it. To do this, click the “Define New Unit” button and enter a name and description for the unit

Once you have created a unit name and description, specify whether the new unit belongs to an existing unit type, or to a new custom unit type.

Defining a new unit based on one of the existing unit types.

After choosing or defining the unit, specify the precision of the data in the Precision field. For example, if the attribute is measured in meters, a precision of “0.1” would be interpreted as precise to the nearest 1/10th of a meter. You must also choose the number type used by the data: natural, whole, integer, or real. The four number types in the drop-down menu are not discrete classes some overlap. Remember to choose the type that most specifically and accurately describes the data in the attribute or column you are defining. Optionally, you can provide the minimum and maximum values for the data column by clicking the Add button beside the Bounds field at the bottom of the screen.

The four number types used by data attributes.	
Number Type	Description
Natural numbers	Natural numbers are positive and non-zero counting numbers (i.e., non-fractions), such as 1, 2, 3, and so on. They cannot be negative or zero. When thinking of counting numbers, think about counting a basket of oranges, or counting something using your fingers (although natural numbers can be larger than ten). There are no fractions of oranges or fractions of fingers (hopefully!), and there are no negative numbers of oranges or negative numbers of fingers. Natural numbers are one type of whole numbers.
Whole numbers	Whole numbers are just like natural numbers, except zero is included in the set of whole numbers, and therefore whole numbers are positive counting numbers and zero: 0, 1, 2, 3, and so on. Just like natural numbers, they cannot be fractions or negative. Whole numbers are a type of integer, and they include natural numbers.

Integer numbers	Integers are just like whole numbers, except negative counting numbers are included in this set. Therefore, integers are positive and negative counting numbers and zero, such as -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, and so on. Just like whole and natural numbers they cannot be fractions. Integers are a type of rational numbers, and they include whole numbers and natural numbers.
Real numbers	Real numbers are the broadest set of numbers. They can be negative and positive fractions and counting numbers, and can include zero. Therefore, a list of numbers like the following would be a set of real numbers: -1/2, -0.25, 3.14, 0, 1, -25, 5/8, and so on. As you can see from this list of examples, real numbers include integers, whole numbers, and natural numbers.

The screenshot shows a form for defining a Date-Time field. It includes options for Category (Unordered, Ordered, Relative, Absolute, Date-Time), a Format input field, Precision representation, and a list of Bounds. Two yellow callout boxes provide instructions: 'Specify the date format using a format string (e.g., YYYY-MM-DD)' pointing to the Format field, and 'Click Add to specify a lower and upper bound for the date/time data.' pointing to the Add button.

Absolute (ratio) Absolute (ratio) The absolute, or ratio, scale is an interval scale with a meaningful zero point.

Date-Time Incorporate the date following the ISO 8601 standard: **year-month-day (YYYY-MM-DD)**

Representation according to ISO 8601	possible values
Year and)	YYYY, four digits
month (M)	MM, from 01 to 12
Day D)	DD, day from 1 to 31

i.e.: 2023-09-14

HOURL

Enter the time following the ISO 8601 standard) hh:mm:ss

Hour (H)	hh , from 00 to 23, 24:00:00 as last minute
----------	---

i.e. .: 20:15:00

Completing the Wizard

After you have finished entering a description for each of the attributes, click "Finish" to finish documenting the data table, and then save the data package to save your changes.

New Data Table Wizard

Data Information:

Table (Entity)

Enter some information about the data table contained in your file. If you have more than one data table, additional tables may be added after the completion of this wizard.

Table name: Population sampling data for zooplankton in the Great Lakes, 2000

Enter a paragraph that describes the table or entity, its type, and relevant information about the data that it contains.
[Example: Species abundance data for 1996 at the VCR LTER site]

Description

One or more attributes (columns) must be defined:

Attribute Name	Attribute Definition	Measurement Scale
Date	The day, month, and year that sa...	datetime

Attributes

Each described attribute (i.e., data column) will be listed in the Attribute window. Click Add to add additional attribute documentation or select an attribute and then click the Edit button to edit the documentation.

Click Next after all attributes have been documented to complete the Data Table Wizard.

Buttons: Save for Later, Cancel, < Back, Next >, Finish

New Data Table Wizard

New Data Table Wizard

Summary

This wizard has now collected all the information that is required to create your new data table.

You can press the "Finish" button to add the data table to your package.

If you want to add more data tables to your package, select the "Create/Import New Data Table..." option from the "Data" menu or [click here](#) to finish this wizard and add a new data table now.

Click the link to complete the data documentation and immediately add a new data table using the Data Table Wizard.

Click Finish to complete the documentation and view the Data Package.

Buttons: Save for Later, Cancel, < Back, Next >, Finish

Importing Documentation

If you choose to import a data table, you can simplify the process of entering documentation by choosing to automatically extract it from the table.

If the first row contains column labels, then check the box beside the “Column labels are in starting row” setting.

Note that Morpho automatically places extracted codes in the table under "Code", but you must provide the code definitions. You must also provide column definitions (Morpho does not do this automatically).

Adding Other Data Table Types (E.g., Excel, Mathematica, HTML, or XML)

Stored data, such as Excel, Mathematica, or Word documents, can be added to data packages using the data table wizard.

But note that applications such as Excel and Microsoft Access also allow you to export data as a simple delimited file, which can be imported into

Adding an Excel or other data file to a data package.

Stored data, such as Excel, Mathematica, or Word documents, can be added to data packages using the data table wizard.

But keep in mind that applications like Excel and Microsoft Access also allow you to export data as a simple delimited file, which can be imported into Morpho and viewed.

To add a file to a data pack:

1. Open the data package in which you want to save the data file. From the Data menu at the top of the Data Package screen, select Create/Import New Data Table. The data table wizard opens.
2. In the data table wizard, select "Import" and "Manual", Click the locate button to select the file to import. Click Next.
3. On the Data Table Wizard File Format screen, select "Externally Defined Non-Text or Proprietary Format" and then choose the appropriate format from the list, or "other" if the data format does not appear in the list

Note: It is often preferable to import image files as "other entities"

Once you have identified the data file and its format, use the data table wizard to document it as you would a delimited text file

Adding a non-text or proprietary file to a data package.

NOTE Complex, geospatially indexed images can be included in data packages and described in EML 2.0 and newer versions using the “spatial Raster” or “spatial Vector” entity modules. However, the Morpho do not support adding documentation to these modules.

Adding Other Data Entities (E.g. binary files, images, PDFs)

Data files (scanned PDF field notes, jpeg images) must be imported as "other entities".

To add other data entities to a data package:

Open the data package in which you want to save the data file. From the Data menu at the top of the Data Pack screen, select "Import Other Data."

Select the file to be imported. Click the “locate” button to select the file to import.

Click “Ok”. Basic file metadata (file type and file size) will be collected automatically.

Existing Data Tables can have their data replaced while still preserving the original metadata that was so meticulously entered during the initial import. This allows a data table to be described before the data is fully cleaned and finalized, thereby making Morpho useful for active data management.

Editing a Data Package

Once a data package has been created, you can edit its documentation in one of the following ways:

- using the Documentation menu items (for most editing)
- using the Morpho Editor

Either tool permits you to change or delete documentation entered.

Save Data Packages

After creating a data package, use Save to save the package to the local machine.

Exporting Data Packages

To save a data package for use outside Morpho, choose to Export the package. To export a package, follow the steps for synchronizing, except choose Export from the drop-down action menu. You can export to a directory or to a .zip file, which will allow you to easily transport the package. If you choose to export to a directory, you will be prompted to select a directory data (if your data package includes data) will be exported to the specified directory.

EXPORT TO A .ZIP FILE

More information regarding the morpho application can be found at:

<https://knb.ecoinformatics.org/software/dist/MorphoUserGuide.pdf>